

R.A. Greenberg's snRNAseq Analysis Tutorial: Investigating molecular adaptations to torpor in squirrel DRG neurons

2023-2024

Introduction

Welcome to R.A.G's 2023-2024 snRNAseq analysis. A few things to note: I aimed to justify my decisions wherever possible, and to be the least wrong possible. It doesn't mean my work is right or optimal. In fact, I encourage you to think about what is best for your specific data and analysis goals – it's probably NOT what I am doing.

P.S. Lastly, don't forget: RNAseq analysis is an ever-evolving technique. Nobody knows what they are doing either. At the end of the day, the only "best" method is the one you can justify to yourself -- and wholeheartedly believe.

Library installation

```
library(Seurat)
library(SeuratObject)
library(sctransform)
library(tibble)
library(ggplot2)
library(glmGamPoi)
library(devtools)
library(SoupX)
library(DoubletFinder)
library(SeuratWrappers)
library(pesto)
library(stringr)
library(matrixStats)
library(Matrix)
library(DESeq2)
library(openxlsx)
library(tinytex)
library(formatR)
library(pagedown)
```

Gene lists

Used during exploration of results from analyses

```
mechano_related <- c("Piezo2", "Piezo1", "Kcnk2", "Kcnk4", "Tmem150c",
  "Mdfic", "Mdfi", "Tmem87a", "Tmem100", "Tmem63b", "Tmem63a",
  "Tmem63c")

markers_expand <- c("Nefh", "Ntrk3", "Hapln4", "Htr3a", "Cplx2",
  "Pvalb", "Cadps2", "Ntrk2", "Scn5a", "Fam19a1", "Calb1",
  "Th", "Tafa4", "Zfp521", "Gfra2", "Znf521", "P2ry1", "Mrgprd",
  "Mrgpra3", "Lpar3", "P2rx3", "Cd55", "Trpc3", "Sst", "Il13lra",
  "Nppb", "Tac1", "Adcyap1", "Gal", "Cartpt", "Trpm8", "Gpr26",
  "Sstr2", "Gpx3", "Hpc4", "Atp2b4")

Trp_less <- c("Trpa1", "Trpc6", "Trpm8", "Trpv1")

mempot <- c("Atp1a1", "Atp1a2", "Atp1a3", "Atp1b1", "Atp1b2",
  "Atp1b3", "Hcn1", "Nalcn", "Kcnk1", "Kcnk2", "Kcnk3", "Kcnk4",
  "Kcnk5", "Kcnk6", "Kcnk7", "Kcnk8", "Kcnk9", "Kcnk10", "Kcnk11",
  "Kcnk12", "Kcnk13", "Kcnk14", "Kcnk15", "Kcnk16", "Kcnk17",
  "Kcnk18", "Kcnk19", "Kcnk20")

Vgsc_ab <- c("Scn1a", "Scn8a", "Scn5a", "Scn9a", "Scn10a", "Scn11a",
  "Scn1b", "Scn2b", "Scn3b", "Scn4b")

Vgpc_1 <- c("Kcna1", "Kcna2", "Kcna3", "Kcna4", "Kcna5", "Kcna6",
  "Kcna7", "Kcna8", "Kcna9", "Kcna10", "Kcnb1", "Kcnb2", "Kcnc1",
  "Kcnc2", "Kcnc3", "Kcnc4", "Kcnf1", "Kcng1", "Kcng2", "Kcng3",
  "Kcng4", "Kcnh1", "Kcnh2", "Kcnh3", "Kcnh4", "Kcnh5", "Kcnh6",
  "Kcnh7", "Kcnh8", "Kcnq1", "Kcnq2", "Kcnq3", "Kcnq4", "Kcnq5",
  "Kcns1", "Kcns2", "Kcns3", "Kcnv1", "Kcnv2")

Opioid <- c("Oprd1", "Oprk1", "Oprm1", "Oprl1")
```

Where to start?

This tutorial assumes familiarity with the below Seurat tutorial, which is my main reference. I suggest you read that tutorial before reading mine further, as this work does not aim to replace or repeat it. In addition, please note that references that are NOT the below citation are included in each code block for your convenience.

```
# 'Seurat - Guided Clustering Tutorial', compiled: October
# 31, 2023.
# https://satijalab.org/seurat/articles/pbmc3k\_tutorial.html.
```

Load filtered matrices

Here I am loading filtered matrices from CellRanger output. I am loading multiple matrices into one big matrix list. Lists are how you can handle analysis of multiple samples at once – whether in matrix or seurat object form. So you will repeatedly see the code pattern below, where I define an empty list, and ultimately fill it with modified objects at the end.

```
# Set the base directory path
base_dir <- "/home/rg828/ycga_work/new112023/"

# Set the prefixes, numbers, and suffixes
prefixes <- c("tsqDRG", "asqDRG")
numbers <- 1:5
suffixes <- c("F", "M")

# Initialize a list to store the loaded matrices
filt_matrices <- list()

# Loop through each combination of prefix, number, and
# suffix
for (prefix in prefixes) {
  for (number in numbers) {
    for (suffix in suffixes) {
      # Construct the file path for each sample
      file_path <- file.path(base_dir, paste0("RG_", prefix,
        number, "_", suffix, "/outs/filtered_feature_bc_matrix.h5"))

      # Check if the file path exists before loading
      # data
      if (file.exists(file_path)) {
        # Use Read10X_h5 function to load the data
        matrix_data <- Read10X_h5(filename = file_path,
          use.names = TRUE)

        # Create a unique identifier for the loaded
        # matrix (adjust as needed)
        i <- paste0(prefix, number, "_", suffix, "_filt")

        # Store the loaded matrix in the list
        filt_matrices[[i]] <- matrix_data
      }
    }
  }
}

saveRDS(filt_matrices, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_filt_matrices.rds")
```

Save your list of filtered matrices for later use! This allows you to avoid redoing slow and expensive computations over and over again... Most everything you can save as an RDS.

You can then redownload it later:

```
sq_filt_matrices <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_filt_matrices.rds")
```

Load raw matrices

Raw matrices are rarely used in Seurat clustering tutorials, but I will use these for SoupX.

```

# Set the base directory path
base_dir <- "/home/rg828/ycga_work/new112023/"

# Set the prefixes, numbers, and suffixes
prefixes <- c("sqDRG")
numbers <- 1:5
suffixes <- c("F", "M")

# Initialize a list to store the loaded matrices
raw_matrices <- list()

# Input variable raw_matrices <- sq_raw_matrices

# Loop through each combination of prefix, number, and
# suffix
for (prefix in prefixes) {
  for (number in numbers) {
    for (suffix in suffixes) {
      # Construct the file path for each sample
      file_path <- file.path(base_dir, paste0("RG_", prefix,
        number, "_", suffix, "/outs/raw_feature_bc_matrix.h5"))

      # Check if the file path exists before loading
      # data
      if (file.exists(file_path)) {
        # Use Read10X_h5 function to load the data
        matrix_data <- Read10X_h5(filename = file_path)

        # Create a unique identifier for the loaded
        # matrix (adjust as needed)
        i <- paste0(prefix, number, "_", suffix, "_raw")

        # Store the loaded matrix in the list
        raw_matrices[[i]] <- matrix_data
      }
    }
  }
}

saveRDS(raw_matrices, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_raw_matrices.rds")

```

Make seurat objects

```

# Initialize list
seurats <- list()
filt_matrices <- list()

# Input variable seurats <- sq_seurats
filt_matrices <- sq_filt_matrices

# Loop through each loaded matrix
for (i in names(filt_matrices)) {
  # Create Seurat object
  s <- CreateSeuratObject(counts = filt_matrices[[i]])
  # Store additional information if needed
  s$SampleID <- i
  # Store the Seurat object in the list
  seurats[[i]] <- s
}

saveRDS(seurats, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_seurats.rds")

```

Figure out significant PCs for clustering.

ElbowPlot

As of 2023, Seurat tutorial recommends ElbowPlot for figuring out significant PCs. Let's try on sample 1 with 50 PCs, then 100 PCs:

```

sq_seurats <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_seurats.rds")

seurats <- sq_seurats

# 50 PCs

# lists
sct_objects <- list()
pca_objects <- list()
elbow_plots <- list()

# Perform SCTransform, a new normalization method by Seurat
# developers
sct_objects[[1]] <- SCTransform(seurats[[1]])
# Perform RunPCA
pca_objects[[1]] <- RunPCA(sct_objects[[1]], npcs = 50)
elbow_plots[[1]] <- ElbowPlot(object = pca_objects[[1]], ndims = 50,
  reduction = "pca")

elbow_plots[[1]]

```



```

# 100 PCs
pca_objects[[1]] <- RunPCA(sct_objects[[1]], npcs = 100)
elbow_plots[[1]] <- ElbowPlot(pca_objects[[1]], ndims = 100)

elbow_plots[[1]]

```


Can YOU see an elbow? I never could, and found that while elbows are quite clear in smaller datasets (see Seurat tutorial), this was utterly frustrating for my data. In fact, the more components I do in my elbows, the farther along the “elbow” seems! I decided to go back to older versions of Seurat to use a quantitative method that is slow but totally worth it for me as it spits out the significance of each principal component: JackStraw.

JackStraw

```
# Here's the code for a whole list of samples:

# Initialize list
seurats <- list()

# input variable
seurats <- sq_seurats

# get the significant PCs.
for (i in names(seurats)) {

  seurats[[i]] <- NormalizeData(seurats[[i]])
  seurats[[i]] <- FindVariableFeatures(seurats[[i]])
  seurats[[i]] <- ScaleData(seurats[[i]], features = rownames(seurats[[i]]))
  seurats[[i]] <- RunPCA(seurats[[i]], features = VariableFeatures(object = seurats[[i]]),
    npcs = 80)
  seurats[[i]] <- JackStraw(object = seurats[[i]], num.replicate = 100,
    dims = 70)
  ScoreJackStraw(object = seurats[[i]], dims = 1:70, do.plot = TRUE)
}

# Ref: Seurat vignette no longer has JackStraw, what a
# shame. I found vignette for use of sample functions at
# biostars: https://www.biostars.org/p/9489752/.

# Let's check out my first sample here:
```


You can see that the last significant component was 55 for this sample. Ultimately, I determined the number of PCs I was going to use by including the last significant component across my samples. In my case, this was 60 PCs.

Note, if your last PC is still significant for a given sample, you can always rerun JackStraw with more dimensions (meaning you also need to run the preceding PCA with more dimensions). You will then be able to catch at which number of dimensions PCs lose significance in that sample.

Cluster your data

PCs: I used 60, per computation of the maximal significant components across my dataset (see above). I then set all dims to 60 for the other functions as well.

Resolution: the clustering tutorial recommends resolution 0.4 - 1.2. I decided to use the lowest resolution inside this range (0.5), with a mental note to expand as needed. I never found a reason to do more as I always had more clusters than seemed biologically relevant! My rule of thumb is that I generally I stick with less (components, resolution, etc) unless I need to do more.

```
# Initialize list
seurats <- list()

# input variable
seurats <- sq_seurats

sct_objects <- list()
pca_objects <- list()

# Loop through each Seurat object
for (i in names(seurats)) {
  # Perform SCTransform
  sct_objects[[i]] <- SCTransform(seurats[[i]])

  # Perform RunPCA
  pca_objects[[i]] <- RunPCA(sct_objects[[i]], npcs = 60)
  seurats[[i]] <- FindNeighbors(pca_objects[[i]], dims = 1:60)
  seurats[[i]] <- FindClusters(seurats[[i]], resolution = 0.5)
  seurats[[i]] <- RunUMAP(seurats[[i]], dims = 1:60)
}

saveRDS(seurats, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster.rds")
```

Plot

```
# Let's see my plots:

sq_cluster <- readRDS("/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster.rds")

# Input variable
seurats <- sq_cluster

for (i in names(seurats)) {
  sample_name <- gsub("[^_]+$", "", i) # Remove everything after the last underscore
  cat(sample_name, "\n")
  print(DimPlot(seurats[[i]], reduction = "umap", label = TRUE))
}
}
```

tsqDRG1_F

tsqDRG2_M

tsqDRG3_F

asqDRG1_F

asqDRG2_F


```
## asqDRG3_M
```



```
## asqDRG4_F
```


Remove background using SoupX

Why?

Let's observe what happens to Scn11a expression in my current data:

```
print(VlnPlot(seurat[[1]], "Scn11a"))
```


This is Nav 1.9, which is only expressed in nociceptors. You can see here how my data seems to say every cluster is expressing it. This unlikely to be true. Instead, looks like I have particularly high background contamination! Let's get rid of it using SoupX, which removes background RNA.

Note you have two options: Soup using your clustering info, soup using CellRanger automatic clusters. As suggested in the SoupX tutorial, I opted to use info from my own clustering for more accurate determination of my contamination.

To do this, I will grab our raw matrix files (remember, we loaded them above!), calculate the rho value of contamination, and remove the contamination from the raw matrices. These filtered matrices will be the seurat objects I will ultimately use for the rest of my analysis.

```

# Initialize lists to store results
soup_results_list <- list()
adjusted_matrices_list <- list()

prefixes <- c("tsqDRG", "asqDRG")
numbers <- 1:5
suffixes <- c("F", "M")

# Get the right variable
seurats <- sq_cluster
# adjusted_matrices_list <- sq_adjusted_matrices_list

# Loop through each sample
for (prefix in prefixes) {
  for (number in numbers) {
    for (suffix in suffixes) {

      # Construct file paths for raw and filtered
      # matrices
      raw_file_path <- file.path("/home/rg828/ycga_work/new112023",
        paste0("RG_", prefix, number, "_", suffix, "/outs/raw_feature_bc_matrix.h5"))
      filtd_file_path <- file.path("/home/rg828/ycga_work/new112023",
        paste0("RG_", prefix, number, "_", suffix, "/outs/filtered_feature_bc_matrix.h5"))

      # Check if the file paths exist before creating
      # SoupChannel
      if (file.exists(raw_file_path) && file.exists(filtd_file_path)) {
        # Use Read10X_h5 function to load raw and
        # filtered matrices
        raw_matrix <- Read10X_h5(filename = raw_file_path)
        filtd_matrix <- Read10X_h5(filename = filtd_file_path)

        # Create SoupChannel for the current sample
        soup.channel <- SoupChannel(raw_matrix, filtd_matrix)

        # Retrieve the Seurat object
        seurat_obj <- seurats[[paste0(prefix, number,
          "_", suffix, "_filtd")]]

        # Get metadata and UMAP coordinates from
        # the Seurat object
        meta <- seurat_obj@meta.data
        umap <- seurat_obj@reductions$umap@cell.embeddings

        # Set clusters in the SoupChannel
        soup.channel <- setClusters(soup.channel, setNames(meta$seurat_clusters,
          rownames(meta)))

        # Set UMAP coordinates in the SoupChannel
        soup.channel <- setDR(soup.channel, umap)

        # Run autoEstCont and adjustCounts
        soup.channel <- autoEstCont(soup.channel)
        adj_matrix <- adjustCounts(soup.channel, roundToInt = TRUE)

        # Store SoupX results and adjusted matrix
        soup_results_list[[paste0(prefix, number, "_",
          suffix)]] <- soup.channel
        adjusted_matrices_list[[paste0(prefix, number,
          "_", suffix)]] <- adj_matrix
      }
    }
  }
}

# Ref: SoupX PBMC Demonstration. Compiled: 2022-11-01.
# https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/SoupX/vignettes/pbmcTutorial.html

```

Let's look at my first sample:

I have a contamination of 30% for this sample, as indicated by rho max. Using my adjustCounts function above, I removed contaminated counts.

```
# Save your filtered raw matrices:

saveRDS(adjusted_matrices_list, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_adjusted_matrices_list.rds")
```

Create a souped up seurat object!

Now we can make a seurat object out of our filtered matrix.

```
# Initialize
seurats <- list()
adjusted_matrices_list <- list()

# Input variable
adjusted_matrices_list <- sq_adjusted_matrices_list

# Loop through each loaded matrix
for (i in names(adjusted_matrices_list)) {
  # Create Seurat object
  s <- CreateSeuratObject(counts = adjusted_matrices_list[[i]])
  seurats[[i]] <- s
}

saveRDS(seurats, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_seurats_spd.rds")
```

Quality Control (QC)

Now that we have removed the background, let's do QC.

A typical QC pipeline involves the removal of cells with high mitochondrial gene expression, low UMIs, and or low genes.

But what is low for my data? Let's look:

```
sq_seurats_spd <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_seurats_spd.rds")

seurats <- sq_seurats_spd

for (i.seurat in names(seurats)) {
  sample_name <- gsub("[^_]+$", "", i)
  cat("For sample", sample_name, ":", "\n")
  print(VlnPlot(seurats[[i.seurat]], features = c("nFeature_RNA",
    "nCount_RNA"), ncol = 3))
  cat("Summary of nCount_RNA:\n")
  print(summary(seurats[[i.seurat]]$nCount_RNA))
  cat("Summary of nFeature_RNA:\n")
  print(summary(seurats[[i.seurat]]$nFeature_RNA))
}
```

```
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
```



```
## Summary of nCount_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.     Max.
##   471   2248   2954   4958   4301   86560
## Summary of nFeature_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.     Max.
##   369   1470   1705   1894   2065   6001
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
```

nFeature_RNA

SeuratProject

Identity

nCount_RNA

SeuratProject

Identity

```
## Summary of nCount_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##   469   2098   2747   5059   4411   84049
## Summary of nFeature_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##   392   1416   1647   1957   2170   6411
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
```

nFeature_RNA

SeuratProject

Identity

nCount_RNA

SeuratProject

Identity

```
## Summary of nCount_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##   469   1816   2417   4283   3536  140136
## Summary of nFeature_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##   409   1273   1501   1729   1861   6568
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
```

nFeature_RNA

SeuratProject

Identity

nCount_RNA

SeuratProject

Identity

```
## Summary of nCount_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##   428   2092   2641   5156   4005  132063
## Summary of nFeature_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##   355   1426   1608   1840   1958   5377
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
```

nFeature_RNA

SeuratProject

Identity

nCount_RNA

SeuratProject

Identity

```
## Summary of nCount_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##  440.0  945.2  1217.0  2323.7  1859.0  58921.0
## Summary of nFeature_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median      Mean 3rd Qu.      Max.
##   386   763   921   1181   1219   5911
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
```



```
## Summary of nCount_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   447   1827   2370   4103   3681   91187
## Summary of nFeature_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   396   1325   1563   1834   2006   6683
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
```



```
## Summary of nCount_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   418   1535   1982   3314   2995   81745
## Summary of nFeature_RNA:
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   321   1108   1268   1465   1598   4465
```

We can see that for all but asqDRG2, the first quartile is above 1000 UMI for each nucleus in each sample. So I decided

less than 1000 UMI per barcode means the nucleus is junk. I decided to be more generous with genes per barcode, keeping the standard 500 unique genes threshold. I figured it is technically conceivable that a given cell/nucleus expresses many different molecules from a smaller set of genes, but that if it expresses only a small amount of unique molecules, it is most definitely junk.

What about MT filtering? Sadly, using the HiC thirteen-lined ground squirrel genome at least (GCF_016881025.1), squirrel MT genes are cryptic - they are not preceded by “mt-”! You can find them by looking up what all the mouse MT genes are, and then finding all the ortholog genes in squirrel (minus the mt- prefix!), and then telling a function to find this pattern and exclude based on a set of conditions. See below. I decided to use the standard 10% cutoff for MT genes.

The lovely QC pipeline below is adapted from Dr. Viktor Feketa’s code! Enjoy his intricate love of cleaning.

```
sq_seurats_spd <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_seurats_spd.rds")

# Initialize
seurats <- list()

# input variable
seurats <- sq_seurats_spd

# filtering criteria
max.mt.filter <- 10
min.umi.filter <- 1000
min.genes.filter <- 500

pattern <- "^ (ND1|ND2|COX1|COX2|ATP8|ATP6|COX3|ND3|ND4L|ND4|ND5|ND6|CYTB) "

for (i.seurat in names(seurats)) {
  seurats[[i.seurat]][["percent.mt"]] <- PercentageFeatureSet(seurats[[i.seurat]],
    pattern = pattern)
  cat("For sample", i.seurat, ":", "\n")
  print(summary(seurats[[i.seurat]]$nCount_RNA, "\n"))
  print(summary(seurats[[i.seurat]]$nFeature_RNA, "\n"))

  # filter original Seurat with the common filtering
  # criteria
  total.cells.prefilt <- ncol(seurats[[i.seurat]])
  num.cells.high.mt <- sum(seurats[[i.seurat]][["percent.mt"]] >=
    max.mt.filter)
  num.cells.low.umi <- sum(seurats[[i.seurat]]$nCount_RNA <=
    min.umi.filter)
  num.cells.low.genes <- sum(seurats[[i.seurat]]$nFeature_RNA <=
    min.genes.filter)
  num.cells.passing.filters <- sum((seurats[[i.seurat]][["percent.mt"]] <
    max.mt.filter) & (seurats[[i.seurat]]$nCount_RNA > min.umi.filter) &
    (seurats[[i.seurat]]$nFeature_RNA > min.genes.filter))

  print(paste0("cells high MT: ", num.cells.high.mt, " out of ",
    total.cells.prefilt, " (", round(num.cells.high.mt *
    100/total.cells.prefilt, 1), "%)")
  print(paste0("cells low UMI: ", num.cells.low.umi, " out of ",
    total.cells.prefilt, " (", round(num.cells.low.umi *
    100/total.cells.prefilt, 1), "%)")
  print(paste0("cells low genes: ", num.cells.low.genes, " out of ",
    total.cells.prefilt, " (", round(num.cells.low.genes *
    100/total.cells.prefilt, 1), "%)")
  print(paste0("cells passing QC: ", num.cells.passing.filters,
    " out of ", total.cells.prefilt, " (", round(num.cells.passing.filters *
    100/total.cells.prefilt, 1), "%)")

  # filter seurat according to specified filtering
  # criteria
  seurats[[i.seurat]] <- subset(seurats[[i.seurat]], subset = nFeature_RNA >=
    min.genes.filter & percent.mt <= max.mt.filter & nCount_RNA >=
    min.umi.filter)
}
```

```

## For sample tsqDRG1_F :
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   471   2248   2954   4958   4301   86560
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   369   1470   1705   1894   2065   6001
## [1] "cells high MT: 2 out of 26481 (0%)"
## [1] "cells low UMI: 192 out of 26481 (0.7%)"
## [1] "cells low genes: 11 out of 26481 (0%)"
## [1] "cells passing QC: 26287 out of 26481 (99.3%)"
## For sample tsqDRG2_M :
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   469   2098   2747   5059   4411   84049
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   392   1416   1647   1957   2170   6411
## [1] "cells high MT: 0 out of 27554 (0%)"
## [1] "cells low UMI: 322 out of 27554 (1.2%)"
## [1] "cells low genes: 9 out of 27554 (0%)"
## [1] "cells passing QC: 27232 out of 27554 (98.8%)"
## For sample tsqDRG3_F :
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   469   1816   2417   4283   3536   140136
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   409   1273   1501   1729   1861   6568
## [1] "cells high MT: 2 out of 30444 (0%)"
## [1] "cells low UMI: 843 out of 30444 (2.8%)"
## [1] "cells low genes: 20 out of 30444 (0.1%)"
## [1] "cells passing QC: 29599 out of 30444 (97.2%)"
## For sample asqDRG1_F :
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   428   2092   2641   5156   4005   132063
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   355   1426   1608   1840   1958   5377
## [1] "cells high MT: 1 out of 26250 (0%)"
## [1] "cells low UMI: 79 out of 26250 (0.3%)"
## [1] "cells low genes: 12 out of 26250 (0%)"
## [1] "cells passing QC: 26170 out of 26250 (99.7%)"
## For sample asqDRG2_F :
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##  440.0  945.2 1217.0 2323.7 1859.0 58921.0
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   386   763   921   1181   1219   5911
## [1] "cells high MT: 4 out of 29114 (0%)"
## [1] "cells low UMI: 8961 out of 29114 (30.8%)"
## [1] "cells low genes: 291 out of 29114 (1%)"
## [1] "cells passing QC: 20150 out of 29114 (69.2%)"
## For sample asqDRG3_M :
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   447   1827   2370   4103   3681   91187
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   396   1325   1563   1834   2006   6683
## [1] "cells high MT: 0 out of 30465 (0%)"
## [1] "cells low UMI: 205 out of 30465 (0.7%)"
## [1] "cells low genes: 28 out of 30465 (0.1%)"
## [1] "cells passing QC: 30260 out of 30465 (99.3%)"
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   418   1535   1982   3314   2995   81745
##   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
##   321   1108   1268   1465   1598   4465
## [1] "cells high MT: 0 out of 34558 (0%)"
## [1] "cells low UMI: 812 out of 34558 (2.3%)"
## [1] "cells low genes: 41 out of 34558 (0.1%)"
## [1] "cells passing QC: 33746 out of 34558 (97.7%)"

```

```
# Save your filtered objects
```

```
saveRDS(seurats, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_seurats_spd_qc.rds")
```

Sanity check

Did the QC work?

```
sq_seurats_spd_qc <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_seurats_spd_qc.rds")
sq_seurats_spd <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_seurats_spd.rds")

seurats <- sq_seurats_spd

for (i in names(seurats)) {
  meta <- nrow(seurats[[i]]@meta.data)
  print(meta)
}
```

```
## [1] 26481
## [1] 27554
## [1] 30444
## [1] 26250
## [1] 29114
## [1] 30465
## [1] 34558
```

```
seurats <- sq_seurats_spd_qc

for (i in names(seurats)) {
  meta <- nrow(seurats[[i]]@meta.data)
  print(meta)
}
```

```
## [1] 26289
## [1] 27235
## [1] 29607
## [1] 26170
## [1] 20168
## [1] 30261
## [1] 33750
```

```
# Great, our numbers are lower.
```

Remove doublets using DoubletFinder

There are now multiple automated ways to remove doublets, which is convenient. Here, I try DoubletFinder on my data. This method has received positive independent evaluations (see reference below).

```

# First, we prepare our measurements.

# Initialize lists to store results
sweep.stats.list <- list()
bcmvn.list <- list()
optimal.pk.list <- list()
nExp_poi.list <- list()
nExp_poi.adj.list <- list()

for (i in names(sq_cluster_spd_qc)) {
  ## pK Identification (no ground-truth)
  sweep.list <- paramSweep(sq_cluster_spd_qc[[i]], PCs = 1:60,
    sct = TRUE)
  sweep.stats <- summarizeSweep(sweep.list, GT = FALSE)
  bcmvn <- find.pK(sweep.stats)
  optimal.pk <- as.numeric(as.character(bcmvn$pK[which.max(bcmvn$BCmetric)]))

  # Save results to lists
  sweep.stats.list[[i]] <- sweep.stats
  bcmvn.list[[i]] <- bcmvn
  optimal.pk.list[[i]] <- optimal.pk

  # Calculate doublet rate
  doublet.rate.constant <- 0.008 # fraction of doublets per 1000 cells, per the 10X website.
  doublet.rate <- (ncol(sq_cluster_spd_qc[[i]])/1000) * doublet.rate.constant # This is a direct propo
rtion. If we expect .008 doublets per 1000 cells, how many doublets do we expect for the number of cells
(ncol(list[[i]])) in each of my samples ?

  # Calculate nExp_poi and nExp_poi.adj
  annotations <- sq_cluster_spd_qc[[i]]@meta.data$seurat_clusters
  homotypic.prop <- modelHomotypic(annotations)
  nExp_poi <- round(doublet.rate * nrow(sq_cluster_spd_qc[[i]]@meta.data))
  nExp_poi.adj <- round(nExp_poi * (1 - homotypic.prop))

  # Save nExp_poi and nExp_poi.adj to lists
  nExp_poi.list[[i]] <- nExp_poi
  nExp_poi.adj.list[[i]] <- nExp_poi.adj
}

# Save lists as RDS files
saveRDS(bcmvn.list, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/bcmvn.list.rds")
saveRDS(optimal.pk.list, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/optimal.pk.list.rds")
saveRDS(sweep.stats.list, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sweep.stats.list.rds")
saveRDS(nExp_poi.list, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/nExp_poi.list.rds")
saveRDS(nExp_poi.adj.list, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/nExp_poi.adj.list.rds")

# Ref: DoubletFinder:
# https://github.com/chris-mcginnis-ucsf/DoubletFinder Ref:
# 10X doublet statistics:
# https://kb.10xgenomics.com/hc/en-us/articles/360001378811-What-is-the-maximum-number-of-cells-that-can-
be-profiled
# Ref, DoubletFinder evaluation: Xi, Nan Miles, and Jingyi
# Jessica Li. 'Benchmarking computational doublet-detection
# methods for single-cell RNA sequencing data.' Cell
# systems 12.2 (2021): 176-194.

```

Use measurements to calculate doublets: low stringency

Includes low confidence doublets

```

for (i in names(sq_cluster_spd_qc)) {
  sq_cluster_spd_qc[[i]] <- doubletFinder(sq_cluster_spd_qc[[i]],
    PCs = 1:60, pN = 0.25, pK = optimal.pk.list[[i]], nExp = nExp_poi.list[[i]],
    reuse.pANN = FALSE, sct = TRUE)
  dimplot <- DimPlot(sq_cluster_spd_qc[[i]], group.by = paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_",
    optimal.pk.list[[i]], "_", nExp_poi.list[[i]])) & NoAxes()
  print(dimplot)
}

saveRDS(sq_cluster_spd_qc, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_qc_db.rds"
)

for (i in seq_along(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db)) {
  # Extract the sample name
  sample_name <- names(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db)[i]

  # Define the filename based on the sample name and
  # title
  filename <- paste0("/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/",
    sample_name, "_", paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_",
    optimal.pk.list[[i]], "_", nExp_poi.list[[i]]), ".jpeg")

  # Create the dimplot
  dimplot <- DimPlot(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db[[i]], group.by = paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_",
    optimal.pk.list[[i]], "_", nExp_poi.list[[i]])) & NoAxes()
  print(dimplot)
  # Save the dimplot as a JPEG file
  ggsave(filename, plot = dimplot, device = "jpeg")
}

```

```
## tsqDRG1_F
```

DF.classifications_0.25_0.05_5507


```
## tsqDRG2_M
```

DF.classifications_0.25_0.01_5975


```
## tsqDRG3_F
```

DF.classifications_0.25_0.005_7032


```
## asqDRG1_F
```

DF.classifications_0.25_0.02_5476


```
## asqDRG2_F
```

DF.classifications_0.25_0.04_3048


```
## asqDRG3_M
```

DF.classifications_0.25_0.03_7321


```
## asqDRG4_F
```

DF.classifications_0.25_0.005_9111

Use measurements to calculate doublets: high stringency

Includes only high confidence doublets. For brevity's sake, plots are not printed below. Note that they are largely similar to the plots above except that they show fewer doublets.

```

for (i in names(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db)) {
  sq_cluster_spd_qc_db[[i]] <- doubletFinder(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db[[i]],
                                           PCs = 1:60,
                                           pN = 0.25,
                                           pK = optimal.pk.list[[i]],
                                           nExp = nExp_poi.adj.list[[i]], # yes use adj this time
                                           reuse.pANN = paste0("pANN_0.25_", optimal.pk.list[[i]], "_", nExp_poi.list[[i]]),
                                           sct = TRUE)

  dimplot <- DimPlot(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db[[i]], group.by = paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_", optimal.pk.list[[i]], "_", nExp_poi.adj.list[[i]])) & NoAxes()
  print(dimplot)
}

saveRDS(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high.rds")

for (i in seq_along(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high)) {
  # Extract the sample name
  sample_name <- names(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high)[i]

  # Define the filename based on the sample name and title
  filename <- paste0("/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/", sample_name, "_", paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_", optimal.pk.list[[i]], "_", nExp_poi.adj.list[[i]]), ".jpeg")

  # Create the dimplot
  dimplot <- DimPlot(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]], group.by = paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_", optimal.pk.list[[i]], "_", nExp_poi.adj.list[[i]])) & NoAxes()
  print(dimplot)
  # Save the dimplot as a JPEG file
  ggsave(filename, plot = dimplot, device = "jpeg")
}

```

Conclusions: DoubletFinder

You can see that generally speaking, across my samples doublets are hitting a spot between the two giant blobs in my UMAP. However, this is NOT consistent. For my first sample (tsqDRG1), you can see that almost all cells in a smaller island are marked as doublets. Turns out (spoiler alert) that these are my non-damaged, unmixed neuronal populations. The fact that DoubletFinder seems to be saying that in my first sample all doublets are in my neurons and almost none occur in my non-neurons/damaged neurons/mixed neuron clusters is suspicious, since doublets are transcriptomically distinct and usually cluster independently of your main neuronal groups! While DoubletFinder could be right of course, it would also mean that my processing here would remove more neurons from a torpid sample than in my other samples. This would create a significant processing artifact in neuronal number from the get-go! I decided to not use DoubletFinder – whose workings I could not intellectually verify myself – and instead decided to create my own customized doublet filtering system where I would only prioritize removal of neuronal-non neuronal cells, since we care about neurons. What about neuron-neuron doublets, you may ask? Removing neuron-neuron doublets requires an understanding of what is a neuronal subtype in this species in the first place (which is what I'm trying to do here). I decided to not remove neuron-neuron doublets to avoid any premature assumptions regarding squirrel DRG neuron subtype identity.

Note: if you would like to see how I further filtered my samples using DoubletFinder, please see Appendix, Section A.

Remove neuron-nonneuron doublets

Custom pipeline loosely based off of Renthal et al., 2020

In the dawn of time before such nifty automated functions as DoubletFinder existed, folks had to manually remove doublets. Renthal et al used the following criterion: *nuclei expressing neuronal and non neuronal markers* $> 0.5 \times$ *Standard Deviation of mean expression of these markers in all nuclei* are classified as doublets and trashed. I loved the clarity and simplicity of this criterion and decided to use this approach to remove neuron-non neuron doublets.

Workflow overview: To accomplish the above, I (1) make neuron and contaminant lists, (2) find Mean and SD for these genes for all my nuclei and define putative neurons, non-neurons, and doublets based on Renthal's criterion, and (3) remove doublets.

Ref: Methods, Renthal et al., 2020, "Transcriptional Reprogramming of Distinct Peripheral Sensory Neuron Subtypes after Axonal Injury".

1. Make neuron and contaminant (non-neuronal) lists.

Search the literature to make contaminant and neuron lists you will use. The more *verified* markers you use, the more rigorous your search. Note, make sure the markers you use are present in each sample, otherwise this will not work! To that end, you can first do a small search loop to ensure all markers are present (not included below for sake of brevity).

```

sq_cluster_spd_qc <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_qc.rds")

# Initialize list
seurats <- list()

# Input variable
seurats <- sq_cluster_spd_qc

contaminants_list <- list()
neurons_list <- list()

for (i in names(seurats)) {

  contaminants <- as.data.frame(t(as.matrix(seurats[[i]]@assays$SCT@data[c("Sox2",
    "Ednrb", "Cldn5", "Mrc1", "Sparc", "Mpz", "Fabp7", "S100a8",
    "S100a9", "Pecam1", "Pdgfrb", "Notch3", "Kcnj8", "Dcn",
    "Pdgfra", "Tnc"), ])))

  neurons <- as.data.frame(t(as.matrix(seurats[[i]]@assays$SCT@data[c("Snap25",
    "Uchl1", "Elavl2", "Tubb3", "Rbfox3"), ])))

  contaminants_list[[i]] <- contaminants
  neurons_list[[i]] <- neurons

}

```

2. Get neuronal and contaminant Averages and SDs and label putative cell types to identify doublets

```

# Input variable
seurats <- sq_cluster_spd_qc

# Get neuronal and contaminant Averages and SDs

# neurons

TotalNeuronalAvgs <- list()
TotalNeuronalSD <- list()

for (i in names(neurons_list)) {
  # Get neurons data specific to the current sample
  current_neurons <- neurons_list[[i]]

  # Initialize lists to store average and standard
  # deviation for the current sample
  current_avg <- list()
  current_sd <- list()

  # Loop through each column (gene) in the dataframe
  for (col in 1:5) {
    # Calculate the average expression for the current
    # gene
    avg_expression <- mean(current_neurons[[col]])
    sd_expression <- sd(current_neurons[[col]])

    # Assign the average to a new variable with the
    # column name followed by '_TotalAvg'
    colname <- colnames(current_neurons)[col]

    colname_total_avg <- paste0(colname, "_TotalAvg_", i)
    colname_sd <- paste0(colname, "_SD_", i)

    # Add the average expression to the list with the
    # corresponding column name
    current_avg[[colname_total_avg]] <- avg_expression
    current_sd[[colname_sd]] <- sd_expression
  }

  # Append the average and standard deviation for the
  # current sample to the total lists
  TotalNeuronalAvgs <- c(TotalNeuronalAvgs, current_avg)
  TotalNeuronalSD <- c(TotalNeuronalSD, current_sd)
}

```

```

}

# contaminants

TotalContAvgs <- list()
TotalContSD <- list()

for (i in names(contaminants_list)) {
  # Get neurons data specific to the current sample
  current_neurons <- contaminants_list[[i]]

  # Initialize lists to store average and standard
  # deviation for the current sample
  current_avg <- list()
  current_sd <- list()

  # Loop through each column (gene) in the dataframe
  for (col in 1:16) {
    # Calculate the average expression for the current
    # gene
    avg_expression <- mean(current_neurons[[col]])
    sd_expression <- sd(current_neurons[[col]])

    # Assign the average to a new variable with the
    # column name followed by '_TotalAvg'
    colname <- colnames(current_neurons)[col]

    colname_total_avg <- paste0(colname, "_TotalAvg_", i)
    colname_sd <- paste0(colname, "_SD_", i)

    # Add the average expression to the list with the
    # corresponding column name
    current_avg[[colname_total_avg]] <- avg_expression
    current_sd[[colname_sd]] <- sd_expression

    # Print the current results for each gene and
    # sample print(paste('TotalContAvgs for', i, ':',
    # colname, ':', avg_expression))
    # print(paste('TotalContSD for', i, ':', colname,
    # ':', sd_expression))
  }

  # Append the average and standard deviation for the
  # current sample to the total lists
  TotalContAvgs <- c(TotalContAvgs, current_avg)
  TotalContSD <- c(TotalContSD, current_sd)
}

## Get the trash !

# create the result df

trash_list <- list()
result_df_list <- list()
trash <- c()

for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Create an empty vector to store the row names of
  # markers that meet the condition

  # Initialize an empty dataframe to store the results
  result_df <- data.frame(rowname = rownames(neurons_list[[sample_name]]),
    trash_listed = logical(nrow(neurons_list[[sample_name]])),
    neuron_condition = logical(nrow(neurons_list[[sample_name]])),
    contaminant_condition = logical(nrow(neurons_list[[sample_name]])),
    stringsAsFactors = FALSE)

  # Store the trash and result_df in the respective lists
  trash_list[[sample_name]] <- trash
  result_df_list[[sample_name]] <- result_df

  # Loop through each row in the dataframes

```

```

# Loop through each row in the datalist
for (i in 1:nrow(neurons_list[[sample_name]])) {
  # Check conditions for neurons
  neuron_condition <- FALSE # Initialize as FALSE
  for (colname in colnames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])) {
    avg_expression <- TotalNeuronalAvg[[paste0(colname,
      "_TotalAvg_", sample_name)]]
    sd_expression <- TotalNeuronalSD[[paste0(colname,
      "_SD_", sample_name)]]
    expression_value <- neurons_list[[sample_name]][i,
      colname]
    if (expression_value > (0.5 * sd_expression + avg_expression)) {
      neuron_condition <- TRUE # Set to TRUE if condition is met for at least one gene.
      break
    }
  }
  result_df_list[[sample_name]]$neuron_condition[i] <- neuron_condition

  # Check conditions for contaminants
  contaminant_condition <- FALSE # Initialize as FALSE
  for (colname in colnames(contaminants_list[[sample_name]])) {
    avg_expression <- TotalContAvg[[paste0(colname,
      "_TotalAvg_", sample_name)]]
    sd_expression <- TotalContSD[[paste0(colname, "_SD_",
      sample_name)]]
    expression_value <- contaminants_list[[sample_name]][i,
      colname]
    if (expression_value > (0.5 * sd_expression + avg_expression)) {
      contaminant_condition <- TRUE # Set to TRUE if condition is met for at least one gene.
      break
    }
  }
  result_df_list[[sample_name]]$contaminant_condition[i] <- contaminant_condition
}

# Store expression value, standard deviation, and
# average in the result dataframe
for (colname in colnames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])) {
  avg_expression <- TotalNeuronalAvg[[paste0(colname,
    "_TotalAvg_", sample_name)]]
  sd_expression <- TotalNeuronalSD[[paste0(colname, "_SD_",
    sample_name)]]
  result_df_list[[sample_name]][[paste0(colname, "_expression")]] <- neurons_list[[sample_name]][,
    colname]
  result_df_list[[sample_name]][[paste0(colname, "_sd")]] <- sd_expression
  result_df_list[[sample_name]][[paste0(colname, "_avg")]] <- avg_expression
}

for (colname in colnames(contaminants_list[[sample_name]])) {
  avg_expression <- TotalContAvg[[paste0(colname, "_TotalAvg_",
    sample_name)]]
  sd_expression <- TotalContSD[[paste0(colname, "_SD_",
    sample_name)]]
  result_df_list[[sample_name]][[paste0(colname, "_expression")]] <- contaminants_list[[sample_name
]][[,
  colname]
  result_df_list[[sample_name]][[paste0(colname, "_sd")]] <- sd_expression
  result_df_list[[sample_name]][[paste0(colname, "_avg")]] <- avg_expression
}

# Update trash list and mark trash_listed column
for (i in 1:nrow(neurons_list[[sample_name]])) {
  if (result_df_list[[sample_name]]$neuron_condition[i] &&
    result_df_list[[sample_name]]$contaminant_condition[i]) {
    trash_list[[sample_name]] <- c(trash_list[[sample_name]],
      rownames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])[i])
  }
  result_df_list[[sample_name]]$trash_listed[i] <- rownames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])[i] %in%
    trash_list[[sample_name]]
}
}

# You now have a list of nuclei to trash, awesome!

```

```

# SUMMARY

total_neurons_list <- list()
cleaned_non_neurons_list <- list()
cleaned_neurons_list <- list()
non_neuron_list <- list()
trash_list <- list()

for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  neurons_count <- nrow(neurons_list[[sample_name]])

  # Initialize a vector to store row names where
  # neuron_condition is TRUE
  total_neurons <- character(0)

  # Initialize a vector to store row names where
  # contaminant_condition is TRUE
  non_neurons <- character(0)

  # Initialize a vector to store row names where
  # contaminant_condition is TRUE and neuron_condition is
  # FALSE
  cleaned_non_neurons <- character(0)

  # Initialize a vector to store row names where
  # contaminant_condition is FALSE and neuron_condition
  # is TRUE
  cleaned_neurons <- character(0)

  # Initialize a vector to store row names where
  # trash_listed is TRUE
  trash_cells <- character(0)

  # Loop through each row in the dataframes
  for (i in 1:nrow(neurons_list[[sample_name]])) {
    # Check conditions for neurons and contaminants
    neuron_condition <- result_df_list[[sample_name]]$neuron_condition[i]
    contaminant_condition <- result_df_list[[sample_name]]$contaminant_condition[i]

    if (neuron_condition) {
      # Add the row name to the list of total neurons
      total_neurons <- c(total_neurons, rownames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])[i])
    }

    if (contaminant_condition) {
      # Add the row name to the list of non-neurons
      non_neurons <- c(non_neurons, rownames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])[i])
    }

    if (!neuron_condition && contaminant_condition) {
      # Add the row name to the list of cleaned
      # non-neurons
      cleaned_non_neurons <- c(cleaned_non_neurons, rownames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])[i])
    }

    if (!contaminant_condition && neuron_condition) {
      # Add the row name to the list of cleaned
      # non-neurons
      cleaned_neurons <- c(cleaned_neurons, rownames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])[i])
    }

    if (result_df_list[[sample_name]]$trash_listed[i]) {
      # Add the row name to the list of trash cells
      trash_cells <- c(trash_cells, rownames(neurons_list[[sample_name]])[i])
    }
  }

  # Store the lists in the respective variables
  total_neurons_list[[sample_name]] <- total_neurons
  cleaned_non_neurons_list[[sample_name]] <- cleaned_non_neurons
  cleaned_neurons_list[[sample_name]] <- cleaned_neurons
  non_neuron_list[[sample_name]] <- non_neurons
}

```

```
trash_list[[sample_name]] <- trash_cells
```

```
# Print the results for each sample
```

```
cat("For sample", sample_name, ":", "\n")
```

```
cat("Total number of cells:", neurons_count, "\n")
```

```
cat("Total number of neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE):",  
    length(total_neurons), "\n")
```

```
cat("Number of cleaned neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE and contaminant_condition = FALSE):",  
    length(total_neurons) - length(trash_cells), "\n")
```

```
cat("Total number of non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE):",  
    length(non_neurons), "\n")
```

```
cat("Number of cleaned non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE and neuron_condition = FALSE):",  
    length(cleaned_non_neurons), "\n")
```

```
cat("Number of trash cells (trash_listed = TRUE):", length(trash_cells),  
    "\n\n")
```

```
}
```

```
## For sample tsqDRG1_F :
## Total number of cells: 26289
## Total number of neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE): 15907
## Number of cleaned neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE and contaminant_condition = FALSE): 5729
## Total number of non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE): 18536
## Number of cleaned non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE and neuron_condition = FALSE): 8358
## Number of trash cells (trash_listed = TRUE): 10178
##
## For sample tsqDRG2_M :
## Total number of cells: 27235
## Total number of neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE): 17564
## Number of cleaned neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE and contaminant_condition = FALSE): 6920
## Total number of non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE): 17901
## Number of cleaned non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE and neuron_condition = FALSE): 7257
## Number of trash cells (trash_listed = TRUE): 10644
##
## For sample tsqDRG3_F :
## Total number of cells: 29607
## Total number of neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE): 20210
## Number of cleaned neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE and contaminant_condition = FALSE): 7055
## Total number of non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE): 20716
## Number of cleaned non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE and neuron_condition = FALSE): 7561
## Number of trash cells (trash_listed = TRUE): 13155
##
## For sample asqDRG1_F :
## Total number of cells: 26170
## Total number of neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE): 18480
## Number of cleaned neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE and contaminant_condition = FALSE): 6116
## Total number of non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE): 18639
## Number of cleaned non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE and neuron_condition = FALSE): 6275
## Number of trash cells (trash_listed = TRUE): 12364
##
## For sample asqDRG2_F :
## Total number of cells: 20168
## Total number of neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE): 15115
## Number of cleaned neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE and contaminant_condition = FALSE): 6453
## Total number of non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE): 12498
## Number of cleaned non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE and neuron_condition = FALSE): 3836
## Number of trash cells (trash_listed = TRUE): 8662
##
## For sample asqDRG3_M :
## Total number of cells: 30261
## Total number of neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE): 24464
## Number of cleaned neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE and contaminant_condition = FALSE): 7469
## Total number of non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE): 21838
## Number of cleaned non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE and neuron_condition = FALSE): 4843
## Number of trash cells (trash_listed = TRUE): 16995
##
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
## Total number of cells: 33750
## Total number of neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE): 21484
## Number of cleaned neurons (neuron_condition = TRUE and contaminant_condition = FALSE): 8663
## Total number of non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE): 21935
## Number of cleaned non-neurons (contaminant_condition = TRUE and neuron_condition = FALSE): 9114
## Number of trash cells (trash_listed = TRUE): 12821
```

```
# Put this info in metadata:

# Input variable
seurats <- sq_cluster_spd_qc

# First we need the cell barcodes. Where is this info?
# Well, the # of cell barcodes is here in your seurat
# objects:

for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Get the number of columns (barcodes) in the RNA assay
  num_barcodes <- ncol(seurats[[sample_name]]@assays$RNA)
  cat("For sample", sample_name, ":", "\n")
  cat("Number of barcodes:", num_barcodes, "\n\n")
}
```

```
## For sample tsqDRG1_F :
## Number of barcodes: 26289
##
## For sample tsqDRG2_M :
## Number of barcodes: 27235
##
## For sample tsqDRG3_F :
## Number of barcodes: 29607
##
## For sample asqDRG1_F :
## Number of barcodes: 26170
##
## For sample asqDRG2_F :
## Number of barcodes: 20168
##
## For sample asqDRG3_M :
## Number of barcodes: 30261
##
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
## Number of barcodes: 33750
```

```

# Using this knowledge, and the lists of cell identities
# you compiled, go ahead and add all the metadata:

for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Get the cleaned neurons, cleaned non neurons, trash
  # for the current sample
  cleaned_neurons <- cleaned_neurons_list[[sample_name]]
  cleaned_non_neurons <- cleaned_non_neurons_list[[sample_name]]
  trash <- trash_list[[sample_name]]

  # Get the barcodes (column names) of the RNA assay for
  # the current sample
  barcodes <- colnames(seurats[[sample_name]]@assays$RNA)

  # Indicate whether each barcode is in the cleaned
  # neurons, cleaned non neurons, or trash lists!
  in_cleaned_neurons <- barcodes %in% cleaned_neurons
  in_cleaned_non_neurons <- barcodes %in% cleaned_non_neurons
  in_trash <- barcodes %in% trash

  # Add the metadata to the Seurat object
  seurats[[sample_name]]$cleaned_neurons <- as.logical(in_cleaned_neurons)
  seurats[[sample_name]]$cleaned_non_neurons <- as.logical(in_cleaned_non_neurons)
  seurats[[sample_name]]$trash <- as.logical(in_trash)
}

# Check your work here - the number should match
# cleaned_neurons_list...trash_list

for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Count the number of TRUE values in the
  # cleaned_neurons metadata column
  num_cleaned_neurons <- sum(seurats[[sample_name]]$cleaned_neurons)
  num_cleaned_non_neurons <- sum(seurats[[sample_name]]$cleaned_non_neurons)
  num_trash <- sum(seurats[[sample_name]]$trash)

  # Print the result
  cat("For sample", sample_name, ":", "\n")
  cat("Number of cleaned neurons:", num_cleaned_neurons, "\n\n")
  cat("Number of cleaned non-neurons:", num_cleaned_non_neurons,
      "\n\n")
  cat("Number of trash cells:", num_trash, "\n\n")
}

```

```

## For sample tsqDRG1_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 5729
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 8358
##
## Number of trash cells: 10178
##
## For sample tsqDRG2_M :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 6920
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 7257
##
## Number of trash cells: 10644
##
## For sample tsqDRG3_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 7055
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 7561
##
## Number of trash cells: 13155
##
## For sample asqDRG1_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 6116
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 6275
##
## Number of trash cells: 12364
##
## For sample asqDRG2_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 6453
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 3836
##
## Number of trash cells: 8662
##
## For sample asqDRG3_M :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 7469
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 4843
##
## Number of trash cells: 16995
##
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 8663
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 9114
##
## Number of trash cells: 12821

```

```

# Great!

# Visualize the extracted cleaned neurons:

# Loop over each Seurat object
for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Get the Seurat object
  seurat_obj <- seurats[[sample_name]]

  # Create a DimPlot with cleaned_neurons as the grouping
  # variable
  title <- paste("Cleaned Neurons in", sample_name)
  print(DimPlot(seurat_obj, group.by = "cleaned_neurons") +
    ggtitle(title))
}

```

Cleaned Neurons in tsqDRG1_F

Cleaned Neurons in tsqDRG2_M

Cleaned Neurons in tsqDRG3_F

Cleaned Neurons in asqDRG1_F

Cleaned Neurons in asqDRG2_F

Cleaned Neurons in asqDRG3_M

Cleaned Neurons in asqDRG4_F


```
# Visualize the extracted cleaned non neurons:  
  
# Loop over each Seurat object  
for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {  
  # Get the Seurat object  
  seurat_obj <- seurats[[sample_name]]  
  
  # Create a DimPlot with cleaned_neurons as the grouping  
  # variable  
  title <- paste("Cleaned Non-Neurons in", sample_name)  
  print(DimPlot(seurat_obj, group.by = "cleaned_non_neurons") +  
    ggtitle(title))  
}
```

Cleaned Non-Neurons in tsqDRG1_F

Cleaned Non-Neurons in tsqDRG2_M

Cleaned Non-Neurons in tsqDRG3_F

Cleaned Non-Neurons in asqDRG1_F

Cleaned Non-Neurons in asqDRG2_F

Cleaned Non-Neurons in asqDRG3_M

Cleaned Non-Neurons in asqDRG4_F


```
# Visualize the trash:

# Loop over each Seurat object
for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Get the Seurat object
  seurat_obj <- seurats[[sample_name]]

  # Create a DimPlot with cleaned_neurons as the grouping
  # variable
  title <- paste("Trash", sample_name)
  print(DimPlot(seurat_obj, group.by = "trash") + ggtitle(title),
        pt.size = 1, raster = FALSE)
}
```

Trash tsqDRG1_F

Trash tsqDRG2_M

Trash tsqDRG3_F

Trash asqDRG1_F

Trash asqDRG2_F

Trash asqDRG3_M

Conclusions: Custom doublet finder

We can see that cleaned neurons cluster separately from trash, and that trash seems to really hit doublets of neurons and non neurons. Critically, these do not overlap. This makes more sense to me than DoubletFinder's output for my dataset, since I now know what I am looking at and what I am excluding, and all samples look consistent! Yeeehaw

```
# save the new version of your list, w/ metadata  
saveRDS(seurats, "/home/rq828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_qc_unfiltered_0.5SD.rds")
```

3. Subset to remove neuronal-non neuronal doublets

The logic is simple: we just want all cells where trash = FALSE

```

sq_cluster_spd_gc_unfiltered_0.5SD <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_gc_unfiltered_0.5SD.rds")

# Initialize list
seurats <- list()

# Input variable
seurats <- sq_cluster_spd_gc_unfiltered_0.5SD

for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Get the Seurat object for the current sample
  seurat_obj <- seurats[[sample_name]]

  # Get the metadata for the current sample
  metadata <- seurat_obj@meta.data

  # Get the trash list for the current sample
  trash <- trash_list[[sample_name]]

  # Calculate the original cell count
  original_cell_count <- nrow(metadata)

  # Remove cells that exist in the trash list
  seurat_obj_filtered <- subset(seurat_obj, subset = trash ==
    "FALSE")

  # Get the filtered cell count
  filtered_cell_count <- nrow(seurat_obj_filtered@meta.data)

  # Calculate the number of trash cells
  num_trash_cells <- sum(metadata$trash)

  # Print the results
  cat("For sample", sample_name, ":", "\n")
  cat("Original cell count:", original_cell_count, "\n")
  cat("Filtered cell count:", filtered_cell_count, "\n")
  cat("Number of trash cells:", num_trash_cells, "\n")
  cat("Filtered + Trash:", filtered_cell_count + num_trash_cells,
    "\n\n")

  # Store the filtered Seurat object in the new list
  seurats[[sample_name]] <- seurat_obj_filtered
}

```

```

## For sample tsqDRG1_F :
## Original cell count: 26289
## Filtered cell count: 16111
## Number of trash cells: 10178
## Filtered + Trash: 26289
##
## For sample tsqDRG2_M :
## Original cell count: 27235
## Filtered cell count: 16591
## Number of trash cells: 10644
## Filtered + Trash: 27235
##
## For sample tsqDRG3_F :
## Original cell count: 29607
## Filtered cell count: 16452
## Number of trash cells: 13155
## Filtered + Trash: 29607
##
## For sample asqDRG1_F :
## Original cell count: 26170
## Filtered cell count: 13806
## Number of trash cells: 12364
## Filtered + Trash: 26170
##
## For sample asqDRG2_F :
## Original cell count: 20168
## Filtered cell count: 11506
## Number of trash cells: 8662
## Filtered + Trash: 20168
##
## For sample asqDRG3_M :
## Original cell count: 30261
## Filtered cell count: 13266
## Number of trash cells: 16995
## Filtered + Trash: 30261
##
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
## Original cell count: 33750
## Filtered cell count: 20929
## Number of trash cells: 12821
## Filtered + Trash: 33750

```

Make sure I have no trash in my subset, and that I have the right number of each category:

```

for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Count the number of TRUE values in the
  # cleaned_neurons metadata column
  num_cleaned_neurons <- sum(seurats[[sample_name]]$cleaned_neurons)
  num_cleaned_non_neurons <- sum(seurats[[sample_name]]$cleaned_non_neurons)
  num_trash <- sum(seurats[[sample_name]]$trash)

  # Print the result
  cat("For sample", sample_name, ":", "\n")
  cat("Number of cleaned neurons:", num_cleaned_neurons, "\n\n")
  cat("Number of cleaned non-neurons:", num_cleaned_non_neurons,
      "\n\n")
  cat("Number of trash cells:", num_trash, "\n\n")
}

```

```
## For sample tsqDRG1_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 5729
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 8358
##
## Number of trash cells: 0
##
## For sample tsqDRG2_M :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 6920
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 7257
##
## Number of trash cells: 0
##
## For sample tsqDRG3_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 7055
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 7561
##
## Number of trash cells: 0
##
## For sample asqDRG1_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 6116
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 6275
##
## Number of trash cells: 0
##
## For sample asqDRG2_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 6453
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 3836
##
## Number of trash cells: 0
##
## For sample asqDRG3_M :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 7469
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 4843
##
## Number of trash cells: 0
##
## For sample asqDRG4_F :
## Number of cleaned neurons: 8663
##
## Number of cleaned non-neurons: 9114
##
## Number of trash cells: 0
```

```
saveRDS(seurats, "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_gc_filtered_0.5SD.rds")
```

Add useful metadata before integration

It's useful to know what is a torpid sample and what is active, as well as sample ID so that later on you can make plots and figures based off of this.

```

# Initialize list
seurats <- list()

# Input variable
seurats <- sq_cluster_spd_qc_filtered_0.5SD

# add sample id
for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Assign the SampleID to the metadata
  seurats[[sample_name]]$SampleID <- as.factor(sample_name)
}

# add hib state
for (sample_name in names(seurats)) {
  # Check if the sample_name includes 'tsqDRG' or
  # 'asqDRG' and assign the state accordingly
  if (grepl("tsqDRG", sample_name)) {
    state <- "torpid"
  } else if (grepl("asqDRG", sample_name)) {
    state <- "active"
  }

  # Assign the state to the metadata
  seurats[[sample_name]]$state <- as.factor(state)
}

```

```
saveRDS(seurats, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_qc_meta_0.5SD.rds")
```

Integrate your samples

In order to compare across samples with a common baseline, I will integrate my data.

```

# Initialize list
seurats <- list()

# Input variable
seurats <- sq_cluster_spd_qc_meta_0.5SD

integrated_features <- SelectIntegrationFeatures(object.list = seurats,
  nfeatures = 5000)

# prep integration
prep <- PrepSCTIntegration(object.list = seurats, anchor.features = integrated_features)

integration.anchors <- FindIntegrationAnchors(object.list = prep,
  normalization.method = "SCT", anchor.features = integrated_features,
  reduction = "rpca")

saveRDS(integration.anchors, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/integration.anchors_0.5SD.rds")

srInt_0.5 <- IntegrateData(anchorset = integration.anchors, normalization.method = "SCT")
saveRDS(srInt_0.5, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_0.5.rds")

# Ref: 'Introduction to scRNA-seq integration. Compiled:
# March 27, 2023.
# https://satijalab.org/seurat/archive/v4.3/integration_introduction

```

Cluster integrated data

```
# Input variable
srInt <- srInt_0.5

srInt <- RunPCA(srInt, npcs = 60)
srInt <- RunUMAP(srInt, reduction = "pca", dims = 1:60)
srInt <- FindNeighbors(srInt, reduction = "pca", dims = 1:60)
srInt <- FindClusters(srInt, resolution = 0.5)

saveRDS(srInt, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_cluster_0.5.rds")
```

```
srInt_cluster_0.5 <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_cluster_0.5.rds")

# Input variable
srInt <- srInt_cluster_0.5

# plot by sample
print(DimPlot(srInt, split.by = "SampleID", label = FALSE, raster = FALSE,
  ncol = 4) & NoAxes())
```

asqDRG1_F asqDRG2_F asqDRG3_M asqDRG4_F

tsqDRG1_F tsqDRG2_M tsqDRG3_F


```
# plot all
print(DimPlot(srInt, label = T, raster = FALSE, ncol = 4) & NoAxes())
```


Find differentially expressed genes (DEGs) to identify clusters!

```
# Find DEGs in your clusters

# DE test
srInt <- srInt_cluster_0.5

# because SCT is used, need to run PrepSCTFindMarkers first
srIntPrep <- PrepSCTFindMarkers(srInt)

srInt_DE <- RunPrestoAll(srIntPrep, assay = "SCT", slot = "data")
# srInt_DE <- FindAllMarkers(object = srIntPrep) # Jesus
# this is SLOW. Never again.
View(srInt_DE) # You now have a handy dataframe with DEGs!

saveRDS(srInt_DE, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_DE_0.5SD.rds")
```

```
srInt_DE_0.5SD <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_DE_0.5SD.rds")

# let's check it out
head(srInt_DE_0.5SD)
```

##	p_val	auc	avg_log2FC	pct.1	pct.2	p_val_adj	cluster	gene	
##	Mboat2	0	0.8543068	1.967977	0.939	0.361	0	0	Mboat2
##	Acsbg1	0	0.8049839	2.153357	0.796	0.225	0	0	Acsbg1
##	Mapk4	0	0.7946413	2.296487	0.757	0.205	0	0	Mapk4
##	Lrig1	0	0.8161506	2.012833	0.855	0.306	0	0	Lrig1
##	Kank1	0	0.8199251	1.846797	0.894	0.351	0	0	Kank1
##	Gpam	0	0.7954952	2.027250	0.801	0.259	0	0	Gpam

Find putative neuronal clusters based on DEG expression across clusters.

This is the most understated issue in transcriptomics to me. What is a neuron? What is not a neuron? There are no clear answers, and everyone does it a bit differently (if they tell you at all – most papers I read did not describe their criteria at all). The most common way is to use a neuronal marker and define as neurons those clusters where log2FC of that marker, say NeuN, is greater than a certain value, say 0.5. However, note that neurons in different datasets express neuronal markers differently. For instance, my dataset has very low NeuN, or Rbfox3. As it turns out, that did not mean I had 0 neurons! It's worth your time to explore what your dataset is actually expressing.

Ultimately, I figured out which clusters express log2FC > 0.2 for one or more of 4 neuronal markers, including sensory neuron marker Uchl1. I then subsetted those clusters, and then removed damaged neurons and any persistent neuron-non neuron doublet clusters. Finally, I took advantage of the putative neuron labels I had made during my custom doublet

removal pipeline to remove any residual non-neurons and independently verify that these final neuronal clusters were in fact mostly neurons. Turns out that ~90% of them were! This allowed me to be quite confident that, to the very best of my knowledge, I had isolated neuronal populations.

```
# Find clusters likely to be neuronal, non neuronal,
# damaged

srInt <- srInt_cluster_0.5
srInt_DE <- srInt_DE_0.5SD

neuronal_markers <- c("Uchl1", "Elavl2", "Tubb3", "Rbfox3")
logthreshold <- 0.2

# Filter the dataframe for significant markers
significant_markers <- srInt_DE[srInt_DE$gene %in% neuronal_markers &
  srInt_DE$avg_log2FC >= logthreshold & srInt_DE$p_val_adj <
  0.05, ]

# Get unique clusters with significant markers
neuron_clusters <- unique(significant_markers$cluster)

# Print the unique clusters - these are the putative
# neuronal clusters.
print(neuron_clusters)
```

```
## [1] 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 13 14 16 17 18 19 20 22 23 24 25 26 27 31 33 34 39
## 41 Levels: 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 ... 40
```

```
### Neuron plot

# Get all clusters
all_clusters <- levels(srInt@meta.data$seurat_clusters)

# Create a color palette for unique clusters
cluster_colors <- ifelse(all_clusters %in% neuron_clusters, "forestgreen",
  "grey")

# Plot the DimPlot with customized cluster coloring
DimPlot(srInt, label = TRUE, raster = FALSE, cols = cluster_colors) +
  NoAxes()
```



```

### Non-neurons.

Contaminants <- c("Sox2", "Ednrb", "Cldn5", "Mrc1", "Sparc",
  "Mpz", "Fabp7", "Cd79a", "Cd79b", "S100a8", "S100a9", "Pecam1",
  "Pdgfrb", "Notch3", "Kcnj8", "Dcn", "Pdgfra", "Tnc")

logthreshold <- 0.2

# Filter the dataframe for significant markers
significant_markers <- srInt_DE[srInt_DE$gene %in% Contaminants &
  srInt_DE$avg_log2FC > logthreshold & srInt_DE$p_val_adj <
  0.05, ]

# Get unique clusters with significant markers
cont_clusters <- unique(significant_markers$cluster)

all_clusters <- levels(srInt@meta.data$seurat_clusters)

# Create a color palette for unique clusters
cluster_colors <- ifelse(all_clusters %in% cont_clusters, "darkred",
  "grey")

# Plot the DimPlot with customized cluster coloring
DimPlot(srInt, label = TRUE, raster = FALSE, ncol = 4, cols = cluster_colors) +
  NoAxes()

```



```

### Damaged neurons

mito_markers <- c("ND1", "ND2", "COX1", "COX2", "ATP8", "ATP6",
  "COX3", "ND3", "ND4L", "ND4", "ND5", "ND6", "CYTB")
logthreshold <- 0.2

# Filter the dataframe for significant markers
significant_markers <- srInt_DE[srInt_DE$gene %in% mito_markers &
  srInt_DE$avg_log2FC > logthreshold & srInt_DE$p_val_adj <
  0.05, ]

# Get unique clusters with significant markers
mito_clusters <- unique(significant_markers$cluster)

all_clusters <- levels(srInt@meta.data$seurat_clusters)

# Create a color palette for unique clusters
cluster_colors <- ifelse(all_clusters %in% mito_clusters, "black",
  "grey")

# Plot the DimPlot with customized cluster coloring
DimPlot(srInt, label = TRUE, raster = FALSE, ncol = 4, cols = cluster_colors) +
  NoAxes()

```


Cleaned neuronal clusters

What we want for our cleaned neuronal clusters = neuronal clusters - non neuronal overlap - damaged overlap!

```

# which cluster is where
print(neuron_clusters)

```

```

## [1] 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 13 14 16 17 18 19 20 22 23 24 25 26 27 31 33 34 39
## 41 Levels: 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 ... 40

```

```

print(mito_clusters)

```

```

## [1] 1 2 3 5 8 10 11 12 16 18 23 27 28 29 30 31 36
## 41 Levels: 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 ... 40

```

```

print(cont_clusters)

```

```
## [1] 0 1 2 3 5 8 11 12 15 16 21 28 29 30 32 35 40
## 41 Levels: 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 ... 40
```

```
print(length(neuron_clusters))
```

```
## [1] 24
```

```
# remove non neuronal overlap
contaminated_clusters <- intersect(cont_clusters, neuron_clusters)

print(contaminated_clusters)
```

```
## [1] "5" "8" "16"
```

```
neuron_clusters_filtered_RG <- neuron_clusters[!neuron_clusters %in%
  contaminated_clusters]

print(length(neuron_clusters_filtered_RG))
```

```
## [1] 21
```

```
print(neuron_clusters_filtered_RG)
```

```
## [1] 4 6 7 9 10 13 14 17 18 19 20 22 23 24 25 26 27 31 33 34 39
## 41 Levels: 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 ... 40
```

```
# finally remove damaged overlap

print(mito_clusters)
```

```
## [1] 1 2 3 5 8 10 11 12 16 18 23 27 28 29 30 31 36
## 41 Levels: 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 ... 40
```

```
unhealthy_clusters <- intersect(mito_clusters, neuron_clusters_filtered_RG)
print(unhealthy_clusters)
```

```
## [1] "10" "18" "23" "27" "31"
```

```
print(length(neuron_clusters_filtered_RG))
```

```
## [1] 21
```

```
neuron_clusters_filtered_RG <- neuron_clusters_filtered_RG[!neuron_clusters_filtered_RG %in%
  unhealthy_clusters]

print(length(neuron_clusters_filtered_RG))
```

```
## [1] 16
```

```
# your final neuronal clusters for subsetting:
print(neuron_clusters_filtered_RG)
```

```
## [1] 4 6 7 9 13 14 17 19 20 22 24 25 26 33 34 39
## 41 Levels: 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 ... 40
```

Visualize your final cleaned neuronal clusters before you subset

```

### Neuron plot

# Get all clusters
all_clusters <- levels(srInt@meta.data$seurat_clusters)

# Create a color palette for unique clusters
cluster_colors <- ifelse(all_clusters %in% neuron_clusters_filtered_RG,
  "forestgreen", "grey")

# Plot the DimPlot with customized cluster coloring
DimPlot(srInt, label = TRUE, raster = FALSE, cols = cluster_colors) +
  NoAxes()

```


Subset your cleaned neuronal clusters

```

srInt_neurons <- subset(srInt, seurat_clusters %in% neuron_clusters_filtered_RG)
saveRDS(srInt_neurons, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_unfiltered_0.5S
D_0.2log2FCall.rds")

```

Explore identity of cells/nuclei in your cleaned neuronal clusters and produce final neuronal clusters

Final step: Take advantage of cell tags (from my custom doublet removal step) to remove cells labeled as non-neuronal that may be in your neuronal clusters still. In my case that was very low (0.99%), which is great. You can also ask, how many of these cells were actually labeled as neuronal? In my case that was 87%, which suggests that yes, we do have neurons. Next, 12% of my cells were neither labeled as non neuronal or neuronal, and I left them there just to be conservative (they were not labeled as non-neuronal cells, and may still be neurons, so no reason to remove them in my opinion).

```

srInt_neurons <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_unfiltered_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.
rds")

```

```

total <- nrow(srInt_neurons@meta.data)
total # 32814

```

```
## [1] 32814
```

```

neurons <- sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_neurons == TRUE)
neurons # 28653

```

```
## [1] 28653
```

```
non_neurons <- sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_non_neurons ==
  TRUE)
non_neurons # 328
```

```
## [1] 328
```

```
neither <- sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_non_neurons ==
  FALSE & srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_neurons == FALSE)
# 3833 neither
neither
```

```
## [1] 3833
```

```
sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_non_neurons == TRUE & srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_neurons ==
  TRUE) # Nice
```

```
## [1] 0
```

```
trash2 <- sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_non_neurons ==
  TRUE) + sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_non_neurons ==
  FALSE & srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_neurons == FALSE)
neurons + trash2 == total # Yes -- good.
```

```
## [1] TRUE
```

Great! Now, we will remove non neurons, leave undecided ones in there, to be conservative.

```
srInt_neurons <- subset(srInt_neurons, subset = cleaned_non_neurons ==
  TRUE, invert = TRUE)
saveRDS(srInt_neurons, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_filtered_cons_0
.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")
```

Double check your final neurons

```
srInt_neurons <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCa
ll.rds")
nrow(srInt_neurons@meta.data)
```

```
## [1] 32486
```

```
# check:
unknown <- sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_non_neurons ==
  FALSE & srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_neurons == FALSE)
unknown # 3833 unknown cells
```

```
## [1] 3833
```

```
sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_non_neurons == TRUE) # 0 non neuronal cells here.
```

```
## [1] 0
```

```
neurons <- sum(srInt_neurons@meta.data$cleaned_neurons == TRUE)
sum(unknown + neurons) # 32486. Great!
```

```
## [1] 32486
```

Cluster your neurons, get DEGs

You now know the drill...

```

# Cluster !

srInt_neurons <- RunPCA(srInt_neurons, npcs = 60)
srInt_neurons <- RunUMAP(srInt_neurons, reduction = "pca", dims = 1:60)
srInt_neurons <- FindNeighbors(srInt_neurons, reduction = "pca",
  dims = 1:60)
srInt_neurons <- FindClusters(srInt_neurons, resolution = 0.5)

saveRDS(srInt_neurons, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")

DimPlot(srInt_neurons, label = TRUE, raster = FALSE, ncol = 4) +
  NoAxes()

## Get DEGs

srIntPrep <- PrepSCTFindMarkers(srInt_neurons)
srInt_DE_neurons <- RunPrestoAll(srIntPrep, assay = "SCT", slot = "data")

saveRDS(srInt_DE_neurons, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_DE_neurons_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")

```

Neuronal Subtypes

Let's first manually explore and visualize putative subtypes based on a list of verified subtype markers that I configured from the literature. My high certainty groups (≥ 2 markers) are in dark colors, low certainty group (1 marker only) in light colors

```

srInt_neurons <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")
srInt_DE_neurons <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_DE_neurons_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")

# define logthreshold
logthreshold <- 0.5
# Note, if error: you failed to load the right DE and OR
# seurat object OR you forget to set logthreshold!

# Define the function to process marker lists
process_marker_list <- function(marker_list, marker_genes) {
  # Define variable names for markers and clusters
  markers_variable <- paste0("srInt_DE_", marker_list)

  # Filter the dataframe for significant markers
  markers <- srInt_DE_neurons[srInt_DE_neurons$gene %in% marker_genes &
    srInt_DE_neurons$avg_log2FC >= logthreshold & srInt_DE_neurons$sp_val_adj <
    0.05, ]

  # Get unique clusters with significant markers
  clusters <- unique(markers$cluster)

  # Initialize lists to store initial and final clusters
  initial_clusters <- list()
  final_clusters <- list()

  # Loop through each cluster
  for (cluster in clusters) {
    cluster_markers <- markers$gene[markers$cluster == cluster] # Get markers for the cluster

    # Check if cluster has at least two markers
    if (length(cluster_markers) >= 2) {
      final_clusters[[cluster]] <- cluster_markers # Add to final_clusters list
    } else {
      initial_clusters[[cluster]] <- cluster_markers # Add to initial_clusters list
    }

    # Print cluster information
    if (length(cluster_markers) > 0) {
      cat("Cluster", cluster, "has the following markers:",
        paste(cluster_markers, collapse = ", "), "\n")
    }
  }
}

```

```

}

# Define colors for each cluster
light_color <- NULL
dark_color <- NULL

# Define colors based on marker list
if (marker_list == "NF") {
  light_color <- "lightgreen"
  dark_color <- "darkgreen"
} else if (marker_list == "cLTMR") {
  light_color <- "lightblue"
  dark_color <- "darkblue"
} else if (marker_list == "NP") {
  light_color <- "orange"
  dark_color <- "sienna"
} else if (marker_list == "Sst") {
  light_color <- "lightyellow"
  dark_color <- "yellow"
} else if (marker_list == "PEP") {
  light_color <- "pink"
  dark_color <- "darkred"
}

# Define colors for each cluster
cluster_colors <- ifelse(levels(srInt_neurons@meta.data$seurat_clusters) %in%
  names(final_clusters), dark_color, "grey")
cluster_colors[which(levels(srInt_neurons@meta.data$seurat_clusters) %in%
  clusters & !(levels(srInt_neurons@meta.data$seurat_clusters) %in%
  names(final_clusters)))] <- light_color

# Plot DimPlot with color-coded clusters
DimPlot(srInt_neurons, label = TRUE, raster = FALSE, ncol = 4,
  cols = cluster_colors) + NoAxes()
}

# Define NF marker genes
NF_genes <- c("Nefh", "Hapln4", "Htr3a", "Cplx2", "Pvalb", "Cadps2",
  "Ntrk2", "Scn5a", "Fam19a1", "Calb1")

# Define cLTMR marker genes
cLTMR_genes <- c("Th", "Tafa4", "Zfp521", "Gfra2", "Znf521",
  "P2ry1")

# Define NP marker genes
NP_genes <- c("Mrgprd", "Mrgpra3", "Lpar3", "P2rx3", "Cd55",
  "Trpc3")

# Define Sst marker genes
Sst_genes <- c("Sst", "Il31ra", "Nppb")

# Define PEP marker genes
PEP_genes <- c("Tacl1", "Adcyap1", "Gal", "Cartpt", "Trpm8", "Gpr26",
  "Sstr2", "Gpx3", "Hpca", "Atp2b4", "Cartpt")

# Call the function for NF
NF_results <- process_marker_list("NF", NF_genes)

```

```
## Cluster 2 has the following markers: Nefh, Cadps2
## Cluster 3 has the following markers: Cplx2
## Cluster 4 has the following markers: Nefh, Cadps2
## Cluster 6 has the following markers: Ntrk2, Scn5a
## Cluster 7 has the following markers: Cadps2
## Cluster 9 has the following markers: Calb1, Scn5a
## Cluster 11 has the following markers: Cadps2
## Cluster 14 has the following markers: Nefh
## Cluster 15 has the following markers: Cplx2
## Cluster 17 has the following markers: Ntrk2
## Cluster 18 has the following markers: Cplx2
## Cluster 19 has the following markers: Cplx2
## Cluster 21 has the following markers: Cplx2
## Cluster 22 has the following markers: Hapln4
## Cluster 23 has the following markers: Ntrk2
```

```
# Call the function for cLTMR
cLTMR_results <- process_marker_list("cLTMR", cLTMR_genes)
```

```
## Cluster 1 has the following markers: Gfra2
## Cluster 3 has the following markers: Gfra2, Znf521, P2ry1
## Cluster 6 has the following markers: P2ry1
## Cluster 9 has the following markers: Znf521
## Cluster 15 has the following markers: Gfra2, Znf521, P2ry1
## Cluster 21 has the following markers: Gfra2, Znf521, P2ry1
## Cluster 25 has the following markers: Znf521
## Cluster 26 has the following markers: Gfra2
```

```
# Call the function for NP
NP_results <- process_marker_list("NP", NP_genes)
```

```
## Cluster 0 has the following markers: Trpc3
## Cluster 1 has the following markers: Lpar3, P2rx3, Trpc3
## Cluster 3 has the following markers: Cd55
## Cluster 7 has the following markers: Trpc3
## Cluster 10 has the following markers: Lpar3, P2rx3
## Cluster 11 has the following markers: P2rx3, Lpar3
## Cluster 15 has the following markers: Cd55
## Cluster 16 has the following markers: Trpc3, Cd55
## Cluster 18 has the following markers: P2rx3
## Cluster 19 has the following markers: P2rx3
## Cluster 20 has the following markers: Lpar3, P2rx3
## Cluster 21 has the following markers: Cd55
## Cluster 24 has the following markers: Trpc3, Lpar3, P2rx3
## Cluster 26 has the following markers: Lpar3, P2rx3
```

```
# Call the function for Sst
Sst_results <- process_marker_list("Sst", Sst_genes)
```

```
## Cluster 7 has the following markers: Sst, Il31ra
## Cluster 21 has the following markers: Il31ra
## Cluster 26 has the following markers: Il31ra, Sst
```

```
# Call the function for PEP
PEP_results <- process_marker_list("PEP", PEP_genes)
```

```
## Cluster 3 has the following markers: Atp2b4
## Cluster 5 has the following markers: Tac1, Adcyap1, Atp2b4
## Cluster 9 has the following markers: Trpm8, Gpr26, Atp2b4
## Cluster 10 has the following markers: Trpm8
## Cluster 13 has the following markers: Adcyap1, Tac1, Atp2b4
## Cluster 25 has the following markers: Gpr26, Atp2b4
```

```
# Print the results
print(NF_results)
```



```
print(cLTMR_results)
```



```
print(NP_results)
```



```
print(Sst_results)
```



```
print(PEP_results)
```


If you're anything like me, you might be feeling a bit demoralized from these results. Papers seem to show the Instagram version of subtype classification, where subtypes are perfectly distinct, uniquely expressing known markers to perfection, and now you have the reality. You tried to compile the biggest, most comprehensive list for each subtype, but the data only expresses a few of them. High confidence groups largely do not overlap with other subtypes, which is great, but that is not the case for all classifications (see cluster 9, claimed by PEP and NF, both with high confidence). Moreover, with the exception of the cLTMR group (15,3) and Sst group (7), whose high confidence labeling is uncontested, excluding low confidence classifications would significantly reduce the number of neurons for most subtypes (PEP, NP, NF). This sucks. How can we systematically figure out neuronal subtypes?

Template-based neuronal subtype identification

As you may have guessed from the above, the main obstacle in our attempt to determine DRG neuron subtypes is one of information. The few markers currently sanctioned as reliable markers for each subtype in the DRG neuron literature that do appear in this dataset seem insufficient to confidently distinguish subtype groups. However, many DRG neuron snRNAseq datasets exist with robust subtype classifications that are verified by morphological and functional analyses. Instead of fussing over a manual classification, we can use extant classification data as a template to classify our own unknown subtypes. Rather than using 5 markers only to try to figure out a given group, we are now using the entire transcriptome of thousands of cells that were known to be classified in that group. The amount of information available for this template-based classification is thus incomparable to what can be done manually. This method is robust, meaning that if one marker is somehow missing from our data, no problem. We the users are also blind to the classification, meaning that we will not be tempted to subconsciously relax certain thresholds to output this or other neuronal identity we "feel" is right. Moreover, we can numerically assess each fit based on a predictive score, which helps distinguish any remaining trash clusters from true data. Best of all, anyone could take our dataset and get the same exact subtypes by running this code. Phew! Goodbye wishy washy, hidden methods, and inconsistent classifications. Hello repeatable science.

Download dataset you will use as a template

```
# access data
library(GEOquery)
getGEO("GSE201654_mousegpcynohumanDRG.rds.gz")

# Data source: Jung, Min, et al. 'Cross-species
# transcriptomic atlas of dorsal root ganglia reveals
# species-specific programs for sensory function.' Nature
# communications 14.1 (2023): 366.
# https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-023-36014-0
```

Check out their seurat object

```
ref <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/GSE201654_mousegpcynohumanDRG.rds")
DimPlot(ref)
```



```
# great, looks like a normal seurat!
```

Change template format to match your own

In this case, I had to run SCTransform on their data to make it comparable to my object.

```
srInt <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")

# How many PCs does this object have?
num_components <- ncol(ref@reductions$pca)
print(num_components) # they used 50

# split integrated reference species
obj_list <- SplitObject(object = ref, split.by = "Species")

for (i in names(obj_list)) {
  obj_list[[i]] <- SCTransform(obj_list[[i]])
}

# Re-perform integration using SCTransform.

integrated_features <- SelectIntegrationFeatures(object.list = obj_list,
  nfeatures = 5000)
# prep integration
Prep <- PrepSCTIntegration(object.list = obj_list, anchor.features = integrated_features)

integration.anchors <- FindIntegrationAnchors(object.list = Prep,
  normalization.method = "SCT", anchor.features = integrated_features,
  reduction = "rpca")

saveRDS(integration.anchors, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/integration.anchors_Jung2023.rds")

srInt_Jung2023ref <- IntegrateData(anchorset = integration.anchors_Jung2023,
  normalization.method = "SCT")

saveRDS(srInt_Jung2023ref, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_Jung2023ref.rds")

# Reference:
# https://satijalab.org/seurat/articles/integration_mapping
```

Label your dataset using the re-formatted reference

Now that both my ref and my object have an SCT assay, get the labels:

```

srInt <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")
ref <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_Jung2023ref.rds")
# now SCT ref

anchors <- FindTransferAnchors(reference = ref, query = srInt,
  dims = 1:50, reference.assay = "integrated", query.assay = "integrated")

predictions <- TransferData(anchorset = anchors, refdata = ref$celltype,
  dims = 1:50) # predicting cell labels!

srInt <- AddMetaData(srInt, metadata = predictions)
saveRDS(srInt, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")

```

Plot

```

# plot

srInt <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall.rds")

table(srInt$predicted.id)

```

```

##
## AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 C-LTMR P2ry1 Cold Trpm8
## 5872 1463 3889 1492
## NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 NP2 Gfra1 NP3 Sst PEP1 Adcyap1
## 4127 5329 1558 3093
## PEP2 Fam19a1 PEP2 Ntrk1
## 4079 1584

```

```

DimPlot(srInt, reduction = "umap", label = TRUE, pt.size = 1,
  label.size = 4, repel = FALSE) + NoAxes()

```



```

DimPlot(srInt, reduction = "umap", label = FALSE, pt.size = 1,
  label.size = 4, repel = TRUE, group.by = "state") + NoAxes()

```

state


```
DimPlot(srInt, reduction = "umap", label = FALSE, pt.size = 1,  
label.size = 4, repel = FALSE, group.by = "SampleID") + NoAxes()
```

SampleID


```
DimPlot(srInt, reduction = "umap", label = TRUE, pt.size = 1,  
label.size = 4, repel = TRUE, group.by = "predicted.id",  
split.by = "state") + NoAxes()
```

predicted.id


```
DimPlot(srInt, reduction = "umap", label = TRUE, pt.size = 0.8,  
label.size = 4, repel = TRUE, group.by = "predicted.id") +  
NoAxes()
```

predicted.id

Evaluate the reference based mapping

Here, I explore what these predicted IDs express to get a feel for the accuracy myself. We will numerically evaluate subtype assignments afterward. I plot markers, then look at how predicted cell types express markers of interest systematically, where highest-expressing cell types are printed first, and so on.

```
srInt <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0  
.2log2FCall.rds")
```

```
# Plot - are the groups classifying as they say?  
VlnPlot(srInt, "Trpm8", group.by = "predicted.id")
```

Trpm8


```
VlnPlot(srInt, "Ntrk1", group.by = "predicted.id")
```

Ntrk1


```
VlnPlot(srInt, "Ntrk3", group.by = "predicted.id")
```

Ntrk3


```
VlnPlot(srInt, "Gfra1", group.by = "predicted.id")
```

Gfra1


```
VlnPlot(srInt, "Gfra2", group.by = "predicted.id")
```

Gfra2


```

markers <- c("Nefh", "Hapln4", "Htr3a", "Cplx2", "Pvalb", "Cadps2",
  "Ntrk2", "Scn5a", "Fam19a1", "Calb1", "Th", "Tafa4", "Zfp521",
  "Gfra2", "Znf521", "P2ry1", "Mrgprd", "Mrgpra3", "Lpar3",
  "P2rx3", "Cd55", "Trpc3", "Sst", "Il31ra", "Nppb", "Tac1",
  "Adcyap1", "Gal", "Cartpt", "Trpm8", "Gpr26", "Sstr2", "Gpx3",
  "Hpca", "Atp2b4")

avgexp <- AverageExpression(srInt, feature = markers, group.by = "predicted.id")

# Extract the integrated assay matrix
integrated_matrix <- avgexp$integrated

# Convert the integrated assay matrix to a dataframe
df <- as.data.frame(as.matrix(integrated_matrix))

# rowname -> column
df$AverageExpression <- row.names(df)

t_df <- t(df)

df <- data.frame(t_df)

# Highest exp of markers across predicted types:

# Loop through each marker
for (marker in markers) {
  # Check if the marker column exists in the dataframe
  if (marker %in% colnames(df)) {
    # Convert the marker column to numeric
    df[[marker]] <- as.numeric(df[[marker]])

    # Sort the marker column in descending order and
    # store the indices
    sorted_indices <- order(df[[marker]], decreasing = TRUE)

    # Print the sorted marker values along with their
    # corresponding rownames
    cat("Sorted values for", marker, "column:\n")
    print(df[[marker]][sorted_indices])
    cat("Corresponding rownames:\n")
    print(rownames(df)[sorted_indices])
  } else {
    cat(marker, "column not found in the dataframe.\n")
  }
}

```

```

## Sorted values for Nefh column:
## [1] 3.535972e+11 4.319895e+10 5.888328e+07 4.552424e+05 4.017147e+04
## [6] 2.549853e+03 2.618189e+02 1.373653e+02 3.659494e+01 -6.117851e-01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "NP3 Sst"
## [4] "PEP2 Ntrk1" "NP2 Gfra1" "C-LTMR P2ry1"
## [7] "Cold Trpm8" "PEP1 Adcyap1" "PEP2 Fam19a1"
## [10] "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "AverageExpression"
## Hapln4 column not found in the dataframe.
## Htr3a column not found in the dataframe.
## Sorted values for Cplx2 column:
## [1] 4.687441e+04 1.790241e+01 7.557530e+00 4.640133e+00 4.350812e+00
## [6] 4.039516e+00 5.508547e-01 3.018537e-02 -1.159571e-01 -1.931601e-01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "C-LTMR P2ry1" "PEP2 Ntrk1" "NP3 Sst"
## [4] "PEP2 Fam19a1" "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "NP2 Gfra1"
## [7] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "PEP1 Adcyap1" "Cold Trpm8"
## [10] "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "AverageExpression"
## Sorted values for Pvalb column:
## [1] 8.375725e+07 2.576979e+01 -1.764696e-01 -1.815620e-01 -2.087678e-01
## [6] -2.320302e-01 -2.536156e-01 -2.601617e-01 -2.637215e-01 -2.697668e-01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "PEP2 Ntrk1" "C-LTMR P2ry1"

```

```

## [1] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "PEP2 Ntrk1" "C-LTMR P2ryl"
## [4] "PEP2 Fam19a1" "NP3 Sst" "NP2 Gfra1"
## [7] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "Cold Trpm8" "PEP1 Adcyap1"
## [10] "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "AverageExpression"
## Sorted values for Cadps2 column:
## [1] 6.4955300 -0.1378099 -0.2412033 -0.4283293 -0.4906389 -0.4938533
## [7] -0.5299066 -0.5472408 -0.5485343 -0.5605265 NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "PEP2 Ntrk1" "PEP1 Adcyap1" "C-LTMR P2ryl"
## [4] "NP3 Sst" "NP2 Gfra1" "Cold Trpm8"
## [7] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "PEP2 Fam19a1" "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2"
## [10] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "AverageExpression"
## Sorted values for Ntrk2 column:
## [1] 1.515514e+15 1.202258e+15 6.141402e+10 2.776094e+08 2.578956e+05
## [6] 1.340097e+04 1.140643e+02 7.476036e+00 -1.519084e-01 -5.579497e-01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "PEP2 Fam19a1" "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "C-LTMR P2ryl"
## [4] "PEP2 Ntrk1" "NP2 Gfra1" "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3"
## [7] "Cold Trpm8" "NP3 Sst" "PEP1 Adcyap1"
## [10] "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "AverageExpression"
## Scn5a column not found in the dataframe.
## Fam19a1 column not found in the dataframe.
## Calb1 column not found in the dataframe.
## Th column not found in the dataframe.
## Tafa4 column not found in the dataframe.
## Zfp521 column not found in the dataframe.
## Sorted values for Gfra2 column:
## [1] 1.264645e+12 6.294896e+04 6.986677e+02 2.903546e+01 4.331560e+00
## [6] 1.629065e+00 3.586583e-01 -2.090649e-01 -2.701925e-01 -2.790176e-01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "C-LTMR P2ryl" "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "NP2 Gfra1"
## [4] "PEP2 Ntrk1" "PEP2 Fam19a1" "NP3 Sst"
## [7] "Cold Trpm8" "PEP1 Adcyap1" "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3"
## [10] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "AverageExpression"
## Sorted values for Znf521 column:
## [1] 5.722004e+22 1.014988e+09 7.938221e+08 1.997348e+06 4.412298e+05
## [6] 2.421395e+04 2.358865e+03 2.484320e+02 2.693295e+01 1.753966e+01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "C-LTMR P2ryl" "PEP1 Adcyap1" "Cold Trpm8"
## [4] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "PEP2 Ntrk1" "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2"
## [7] "NP2 Gfra1" "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "PEP2 Fam19a1"
## [10] "NP3 Sst" "AverageExpression"
## Sorted values for P2ryl column:
## [1] 2.152922e+06 2.552044e+05 3.201560e+04 9.473834e+01 2.381876e+01
## [6] 1.211705e+01 3.241453e+00 1.116314e+00 -7.470302e-02 -1.163749e-01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "C-LTMR P2ryl" "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "PEP2 Ntrk1"
## [4] "PEP1 Adcyap1" "PEP2 Fam19a1" "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2"
## [7] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "NP2 Gfra1" "Cold Trpm8"
## [10] "NP3 Sst" "AverageExpression"
## Mrgrpd column not found in the dataframe.
## Mrgrpa3 column not found in the dataframe.
## Sorted values for Ipar3 column:
## [1] 3.718242e+10 1.414919e+10 1.946885e+09 1.441642e+07 1.312860e+04
## [6] 1.300595e+03 1.557231e+02 3.233293e+01 4.074047e+00 3.233223e+00
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "PEP2 Ntrk1" "PEP2 Fam19a1" "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2"
## [4] "NP2 Gfra1" "PEP1 Adcyap1" "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3"
## [7] "NP3 Sst" "C-LTMR P2ryl" "Cold Trpm8"
## [10] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "AverageExpression"
## P2rx3 column not found in the dataframe.
## Sorted values for Cd55 column:
## [1] 5.613929e+05 3.799879e+01 9.701806e+00 8.291989e+00 6.140097e-01
## [6] -2.564474e-01 -3.575481e-01 -4.833352e-01 -5.020573e-01 -5.135536e-01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "C-LTMR P2ryl" "PEP2 Ntrk1" "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2"
## [4] "NP2 Gfra1" "NP3 Sst" "Cold Trpm8"

```

```

## [7] "PEP1 Adcyap1"      "PEP2 Fam19a1"      "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2"
## [10] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3"    "AverageExpression"
## Trpc3 column not found in the dataframe.
## Sorted values for Sst column:
## [1] 5.652220e+53 4.899705e+13 1.862919e+13 8.272233e+09 4.420590e+03
## [6] 6.443100e+01 -3.376867e-01 -3.603385e-01 -4.070362e-01 -4.100402e-01
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "NP3 Sst"      "PEP2 Ntrk1"      "C-LTMR P2ryl"
## [4] "NP2 Gfra1"    "PEP1 Adcyap1"    "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2"
## [7] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "Cold Trpm8"      "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2"
## [10] "PEP2 Fam19a1" "AverageExpression"
## Sorted values for Il31ra column:
## [1] 1.898303e+31 2.794990e+17 3.718211e+13 1.104942e+13 1.291123e+10
## [6] 6.874465e+08 7.226563e+06 2.714554e+06 3.428262e+04 5.935229e+00
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "NP3 Sst"      "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "NP2 Gfra1"
## [4] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "C-LTMR P2ryl"    "Cold Trpm8"
## [7] "PEP2 Ntrk1"    "PEP1 Adcyap1"    "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3"
## [10] "PEP2 Fam19a1" "AverageExpression"
## Nppb column not found in the dataframe.
## Sorted values for Tac1 column:
## [1] 9.440365e+53 7.135254e+22 2.621601e+19 1.561101e+16 1.043236e+14
## [6] 6.656212e+13 2.914367e+08 1.239641e+08 7.472948e+06 1.210082e+04
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "PEP1 Adcyap1" "PEP2 Ntrk1"      "C-LTMR P2ryl"
## [4] "NP2 Gfra1"    "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "PEP2 Fam19a1"
## [7] "Cold Trpm8"    "NP3 Sst"         "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2"
## [10] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "AverageExpression"
## Sorted values for Adcyap1 column:
## [1] 3.471007e+15 1.508612e+04 1.789872e+03 1.203944e+03 1.820964e+02
## [6] 1.024803e+02 1.015807e+02 6.308316e+01 1.337182e+01 7.753757e+00
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "PEP1 Adcyap1" "NP2 Gfra1"      "PEP2 Ntrk1"
## [4] "NP3 Sst"      "C-LTMR P2ryl"  "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2"
## [7] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "Cold Trpm8"    "PEP2 Fam19a1"
## [10] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "AverageExpression"
## Sorted values for Gal column:
## [1] 1.116304e+09 1.038718e+09 1.619780e+07 9.927136e+06 2.058909e+03
## [6] 8.504769e+01 6.659568e+00 1.548064e-01 -1.242864e-02 -3.468969e-02
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "C-LTMR P2ryl"    "PEP1 Adcyap1"    "NP2 Gfra1"
## [4] "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "PEP2 Ntrk1"      "PEP2 Fam19a1"
## [7] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "Cold Trpm8"      "NP3 Sst"
## [10] "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "AverageExpression"
## Cartpt column not found in the dataframe.
## Sorted values for Trpm8 column:
## [1] 5.832144e+39 7.437962e+23 3.183266e+14 1.479651e+14 5.814789e+10
## [6] 2.183757e+10 4.812940e+08 1.770930e+05 4.558882e+04 8.999592e+03
## [11] NA
## Corresponding rownames:
## [1] "Cold Trpm8"      "PEP1 Adcyap1"    "NP2 Gfra1"
## [4] "PEP2 Ntrk1"      "PEP2 Fam19a1"    "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3"
## [7] "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "C-LTMR P2ryl"    "NP3 Sst"
## [10] "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "AverageExpression"
## Gpr26 column not found in the dataframe.
## Sstr2 column not found in the dataframe.
## Gpx3 column not found in the dataframe.
## Hpca column not found in the dataframe.
## Atp2b4 column not found in the dataframe.

```

Observations: I can see that overall speaking things make sense - Trpm8 group expresses Trpm8 the most, Sst group expresses Sst the most, etc. Gfra2, which I thought was a bit promiscuous as a good marker to differentiate cLTMR from NPs, is in fact expressed by cLTMR and NP groups, but it does usefully separate NP2 from NP1. Very cool. One that doesn't make sense: Ntrk1 PEP group expresses Ntrk1 way lower than other groups (see graph, see summary). This is likely a bad classification. Can we evaluate this numerically?

Numerically assess matching algorithm

Prediction scores go from 0 to 1, where 1 is a perfect classification. Let's make a copy of our `seurat` object and now say that in this object, if a predicted score is less than 0.5 for a given cell type's classification, then the cell is NA rather than assigned to a group. Given your manual exploration above, are you surprised by which cells become NA?

```
# Let's see if we can now evaluate our cell groupings.

srInt <- srInt
srInt_eval <- srInt

# Ref:

# Cell subtypes we have so far.
table(srInt$predicted.id)
```

```
##
## AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 C-LTMR P2ry1 Cold Trpm8
## 5872 1463 3889 1492
## NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 NP2 Gfra1 NP3 Sst PEP1 Adcyap1
## 4127 5329 1558 3093
## PEP2 Fam19a1 PEP2 Ntrk1
## 4079 1584
```

```
# If a score is less than 0.5, it is ' NA ' .
srInt_eval$celltype <- ifelse(srInt$prediction.score.max > 0.5,
  srInt$predicted.id, NA)
srInt$celltype <- (srInt$predicted.id)

# In grey: no longer a subtype-identified cell! Are you
# surprised by this change?
DimPlot(srInt_eval, reduction = "umap", label = TRUE, pt.size = 0.9,
  label.size = 4, repel = TRUE, group.by = "celltype") + NoAxes()
```



```
DimPlot(srInt_eval, reduction = "umap", label = TRUE, pt.size = 0.8,
  label.size = 4, repel = TRUE, group.by = "predicted.id") +
  NoAxes()
```

predicted.id


```
# meanwhile you can see predicted ID is still intact.
```

```
# Now see numerically: Which classifications decrease  
# dramatically?
```

```
table(srInt_eval$celltype)
```

```
##  
## AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 C-LTMR P2ry1 Cold Trpm8  
## 5310 1381 3493 1438  
## NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 NP2 Gfra1 NP3 Sst PEP1 Adcyap1  
## 3909 4370 1380 2837  
## PEP2 Fam19a1 PEP2 Ntrk1  
## 3574 594
```

```
table(srInt$celltype)
```

```
##  
## AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 C-LTMR P2ry1 Cold Trpm8  
## 5872 1463 3889 1492  
## NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 NP2 Gfra1 NP3 Sst PEP1 Adcyap1  
## 4127 5329 1558 3093  
## PEP2 Fam19a1 PEP2 Ntrk1  
## 4079 1584
```

We see that there is some grey based on cells that weren't confidently classified, especially in our PEP Ntrk1 group. Let's clarify this more by deriving a metric to evaluate cell clusters. We first calculate the ratio of the number of cells that survive in each group given our exclusion criterion above, over total number of originally predicted cells. Then, we print the groups where this ratio is less than 50%.

```
# Calculate the ratio  
ratio <- table(srInt_eval$celltype)/table(srInt$celltype)
```

```
# Print the groups < 50 %  
print(names(ratio[ratio < 0.5]))
```

```
## [1] "PEP2 Ntrk1"
```

```
# There we go, we see our culprit.
```

```
print(ratio)
```

```
##
## AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 C-LTMR P2ry1 Cold Trpm8
## 0.9042916 0.9439508 0.8981743 0.9638070
## NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 NP2 Gfra1 NP3 Sst PEP1 Adcyap1
## 0.9471771 0.8200413 0.8857510 0.9172325
## PEP2 Fam19a1 PEP2 Ntrk1
## 0.8761951 0.3750000
```

```
print(as.table(ratio))
```

```
##
## AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 C-LTMR P2ry1 Cold Trpm8
## 0.9042916 0.9439508 0.8981743 0.9638070
## NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 NP2 Gfra1 NP3 Sst PEP1 Adcyap1
## 0.9471771 0.8200413 0.8857510 0.9172325
## PEP2 Fam19a1 PEP2 Ntrk1
## 0.8761951 0.3750000
```

```
print(data.frame(ratio))
```

```
##          Var1      Freq
## 1 AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 0.9042916
## 2 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 0.9439508
## 3 C-LTMR P2ry1 0.8981743
## 4 Cold Trpm8 0.9638070
## 5 NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 0.9471771
## 6 NP2 Gfra1 0.8200413
## 7 NP3 Sst 0.8857510
## 8 PEP1 Adcyap1 0.9172325
## 9 PEP2 Fam19a1 0.8761951
## 10 PEP2 Ntrk1 0.3750000
```

We can conclude that while for most subtypes, 82 percent or more of originally classified cells make it, less than 50 percent make it for the Ntrk1 PEP2 group. This means we can happily trash this low quality classification and move on.

Let's save our new evaluated object, and our normal untampered object with celltype feature equal to predicted ID:

```
# Let's save our new evaluated srInt object:
saveRDS(srInt_eval, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall_eval.rds")
saveRDS(srInt, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype.rds")
```

Using our above quantitative evaluation, we can confidently remove the cell type group that is not well classified (Ntrk1 PEP2):

```
srInt <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype.rds")
# Exclude cells with the specified label
srInt_subset <- subset(srInt, subset = celltype == "PEP2 Ntrk1",
  invert = TRUE)
table(srInt$celltype)
```

```
##
## AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 C-LTMR P2ry1 Cold Trpm8
## 5872 1463 3889 1492
## NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 NP2 Gfra1 NP3 Sst PEP1 Adcyap1
## 4127 5329 1558 3093
## PEP2 Fam19a1 PEP2 Ntrk1
## 4079 1584
```

```
table(srInt_subset$celltype) # Removed!
```

```
##
## AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3 Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2 C-LTMR P2ry1 Cold Trpm8
## 5872 1463 3889 1492
## NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2 NP2 Gfra1 NP3 Sst PEP1 Adcyap1
## 4127 5329 1558 3093
## PEP2 Fam19a1
## 4079
```

```
DimPlot(srInt_subset, reduction = "umap", label = TRUE, pt.size = 2,
label.size = 4, repel = TRUE, group.by = "celltype") + NoAxes()
```



```
# fantastic, it worked.
```

```
unique(srInt_subset@meta.data$predicted.id)
```

```
## [1] "NP2 Gfra1" "AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3" "C-LTMR P2ry1"
## [4] "PEP1 Adcyap1" "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2" "PEP2 Fam19a1"
## [7] "Cold Trpm8" "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2" "NP3 Sst"
```

```
saveRDS(srInt_subset, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype_subset.rds")
```

Explore output

Alright! We have our subtypes, and we are confident about them, and we can explain to anyone how we got there. Great. Let's start to explore what we have. What I care about is how does cell type identity change during torpor in squirrel DRG neurons? I do this by looking at all cell types on the Y axis, and their corresponding markers on the X axis.

```
srInt <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype_subset.rds")

markers_indataset_highexpression_high <- c("Ntrk3", "Ntrk2",
"Scn5a", "Gfra2", "Znf521", "Trpm8", "Lpar3", "P2rx3", "Trpv1",
"Trpc3", "Sst", "Il131ra", "Tacl", "Adcyap1", "Calca", "Ntrk1") # took the extra pep markers from Jun
g. needed more!

DotPlot(srInt, features = markers_indataset_highexpression_high,
dot.scale = 8, split.by = "state", group.by = "predicted.id",
assay = "SCT", cols = c("blue", "deppink")) + RotatedAxis() +
theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 9))
```


So we mostly have a diagonal line, which means that regardless of state, neuronal subtypes tend to express their markers. Great! However, things start to go haywire right in the middle. We can see that for NP1 and NP2 types we are seeing what looks like different percentages of cells expressing markers based on seasonal state. Also, other subtypes (PEP) seem to express these markers. Is this real?

Pseudobulk to assess DEG based on state

Recent opinion from bioinformaticians & Seurat developers recommends assessing differences between conditions in snRNAseq data with animals as replicates rather than cells (see discussion in reference below) for more accurate results. So what we will do now is to aggregate our data by sample and by state and conduct DEG testing across our animals by state. You need at least 3 replicates per group (torpid, active) to do this.

```
srInt <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype_subset.rds")

srInt_agg <- AggregateExpression(srInt, assays = "RNA", return.seurat = T,
  group.by = c("celltype", "state", "SampleID"))

# each 'cell' is a celltype-condition-sample pseudobulk
# profile
Cells(srInt_agg)

srInt_agg$celltype.state <- paste(srInt_agg$celltype, srInt_agg$state,
  sep = "_")

saveRDS(srInt_agg, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype_subset_agg.rds")

# Ref: 'Differential Expression testing: Perform DE
# analysis within the same cell type across conditions.'
# https://satijalab.org/seurat/articles/de_vignette
```

Do DEG analysis on pseudobulked data by subtype

```

srInt_agg <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5
SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype_subset_agg.rds")
Idents(srInt_agg) <- "celltype.state"

# Set the identities as a character vector
identities <- c("AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3", "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2", "C-LTMR P2ry1",
  "Cold Trpm8", "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2", "NP2 Gfra1", "NP3 Sst",
  "PEP1 Adcyap1", "PEP2 Fam19a1")

# Initialize an empty list to store the results for each
# identity
results_list <- list()

# Loop through each identity
for (identity in identities) {
  # Find markers for torpid and active states
  markers_torpid <- FindMarkers(object = srInt_agg, ident.1 = paste(identity,
    "torpid", sep = "_"), ident.2 = paste(identity, "active",
    sep = "_"), test.use = "DESeq2")

  # Filter markers based on p-value and log2FC
  markers_torpid <- subset(markers_torpid, p_val_adj < 0.05)

  # Add a column for genes
  markers_torpid$Genes <- rownames(markers_torpid)

  # Store the results in the list
  results_list[[identity]] <- markers_torpid
}

saveRDS(results_list, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/insubtypebystate_results_list_
negtoo_0.2log2FCall.rds")

```

Let's explore DEG output

Note: To see how to output comprehensive lists of genes of interest in excel sheet form, see Appendix, Section B.

Here's an example for how to do a quick check for genes of interest.

```

# Note: Lists of genes of interest are at the start of the
# document.

# unpack the dataframe:
results_list <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/insubtypebystate_results_list_negtoo_0.2log2F
Call.rds")

identities <- c("AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3", "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2", "C-LTMR P2ry1",
  "Cold Trpm8", "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2", "NP2 Gfra1", "NP3 Sst",
  "PEP1 Adcyap1", "PEP2 Fam19a1")
# Loop through each identity and unpack the dataframe
for (identity in identities) {
  # Get the dataframe from the list
  df <- results_list[[identity]]

  # Assign the dataframe to a variable with a unique name
  assign(paste("torpid_active_DE_", gsub("\\s", "_", identity),
    sep = ""), df)
}

# Create a function to check for genes in a list and print
# the relevant information
check_genes <- function(df, gene_list, list_name) {
  gene_present <- df$Genes %in% gene_list
  if (any(gene_present)) {
    cat("\nGenes from", list_name, "found in the dataframe:\n")
    print(df[gene_present, c("Genes", "avg_log2FC", "p_val_adj",
      "p_val")])
  } else {
    cat("\nNo genes from", list_name, "found in the dataframe.\n")
  }
}

# Loop through the results_list
for (identity in names(results_list)) {
  df <- results_list[[identity]]
  cat("\nFor subtype:", identity)

  # Check genes from markers_expand
  check_genes(df, markers_expand, "markers_expand")

  # Check genes from Trp_less
  check_genes(df, Trp_less, "Trp_less")

  # Check genes from mechano_related
  check_genes(df, mechano_related, "mechano_related")

  # Check genes from vg pot channels
  check_genes(df, Vgpc_1, "Vgpc_1")

  # Check genes from vg sod channels
  check_genes(df, Vgsc_ab, "Vgsc_ab")

  # mempot
  check_genes(df, mempot, "mempot")

  # opioid
  check_genes(df, Opioid, "Opioid")
}

```

```

##
## For subtype: AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3
## Genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC    p_val_adj      p_val
## Lpar3 Lpar3  -1.688749 1.463301e-15 7.057497e-20
##
## No genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe.

```

```

## NO genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC      p_val_adj      p_val
## Kcnc1 Kcnc1 -0.8819082 2.526458e-09 1.21851e-13
##
## No genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from mempot found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Opioid found in the dataframe.
##
## For subtype: Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2
## Genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC      p_val_adj      p_val
## Scn5a Scn5a -0.9472852 1.118239e-09 5.393263e-14
##
## No genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC      p_val_adj      p_val
## Scn5a Scn5a -0.9472852 1.118239e-09 5.393263e-14
##
## No genes from mempot found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Opioid found in the dataframe.
##
## For subtype: C-LTMR P2ry1
## No genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC      p_val_adj      p_val
## Tmem150c Tmem150c -1.473496 1.491619e-07 7.194073e-12
##
## No genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from mempot found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC      p_val_adj      p_val
## Kcnk1 Kcnk1 -0.5047029 0.04695254 2.264519e-06
##
## No genes from Opioid found in the dataframe.
##
## For subtype: Cold Trpm8
## No genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from mempot found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC      p_val_adj      p_val
## Nalcn Nalcn 0.6534534 0.01379957 6.655529e-07
##
## No genes from Opioid found in the dataframe.
##
## For subtype: NP1 Gfral Gfra2
## Genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC      p_val_adj      p_val
## Lpar3 Lpar3 -2.4130098 8.262992e-28 3.985238e-32
## Gfra2 Gfra2 -0.5086339 1.287896e-02 6.211517e-07
##

```

```

## No genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Tmem150c Tmem150c -0.9517839 2.340977e-06 1.129052e-10
##
## No genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from mempot found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from Opioid found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Oprd1 Oprd1 -1.224765 0.001010812 4.875142e-08
##
## For subtype: NP2 Gfral
## No genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Trpv1 Trpv1 0.2064509 0.003035475 1.464008e-07
##
## Genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Tmem150c Tmem150c -1.415108 1.400235e-06 6.753326e-11
##
## No genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from mempot found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Hcn1 Hcn1 0.4589956 0.003334488 1.608222e-07
##
## No genes from Opioid found in the dataframe.
##
## For subtype: NP3 Sst
## Genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Lpar3 Lpar3 -3.135542 3.891683e-10 1.876957e-14
##
## No genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from mempot found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Hcn1 Hcn1 2.081348 1.65235e-07 7.96928e-12
##
## No genes from Opioid found in the dataframe.
##
## For subtype: PEP1 Adcyap1
## Genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Lpar3 Lpar3 -2.816527 6.728194e-16 3.245006e-20
##
## No genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val
## Tmem150c Tmem150c -1.085956 7.339005e-07 3.539599e-11
##
## No genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from mempot found in the dataframe:
##      Genes avg_log2FC  p_val_adj      p_val

```

```

## Hcn1 Hcn1 0.686379 0.01837502 8.862265e-07
##
## No genes from Opioid found in the dataframe.
##
## For subtype: PEP2 Fam19a1
## Genes from markers_expand found in the dataframe:
## Genes avg_log2FC p_val_adj p_val
## Lpar3 Lpar3 -2.955888 2.420243e-46 1.167282e-50
## Trpc3 Trpc3 4.777608 2.854227e-03 1.376592e-07
##
## No genes from Trp_less found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from mechano_related found in the dataframe.
##
## Genes from Vgpc_1 found in the dataframe:
## Genes avg_log2FC p_val_adj p_val
## Kcnv1 Kcnv1 -1.940938 3.844363e-06 1.854135e-10
##
## No genes from Vgsc_ab found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from mempot found in the dataframe.
##
## No genes from Opioid found in the dataframe.

```

Plot your interesting findings

Notice that now we have the number of dots per plot that represent each sample (in my case, each sample is an animal). I have 3 torpid animals and 4 active animals in this snRNAseq study.

```

srInt_agg <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5
SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype_subset_agg.rds")
srInt <- srInt_agg

VlnPlot(srInt, "Piezo2", group.by = "celltype", split.by = "state",
pt.size = 1)

```



```

VlnPlot(srInt, "Oprd1", group.by = "celltype", split.by = "state",
pt.size = 1)

```



```
VlnPlot(srInt, "Hcn1", group.by = "celltype", split.by = "state",
  pt.size = 1)
```



```
# you can do specific subtypes:
Idsents(srInt) <- "celltype"
Idsents <- c("PEP2 Fam19a1", "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2")
VlnPlot(srInt, "Trpc3", group.by = "celltype", split.by = "state",
  idsents = Idsents, pt.size = 1)
```


Comments: As a visual complement to the quick check above, we can appreciate that mechano-related genes such as Piezo2 are quite steady. But there's evidence of potential excitability changes in nociceptors. You can see as a general trend that the delta opioid receptor Oprd1 is highly expressed in nociceptors in the active state (inhibiting nociception), but that expression in nociceptors gets knocked down during torpor, suggesting disinhibition of nociception. Most interesting, the significant decrease is in NP nociceptors, involved in mechanical hypersensitivity. Similarly, Hcn1, hyperpolarization-activated channel (which typically enhances excitability) is selectively upregulated in nociceptors, including 2/3 NP groups. Finally, we see that NP marker Trpc3 is now significantly expressed in another nociceptor group (PEP). Ectopic expression of NP markers has been shown to cause mechanical hypersensitivity. So overall, looks like we have transcriptional expansion of NP groups, as well as excitation and disinhibition of these groups. Cool leads for functional follow up experiments!

Do DEG analysis on pseudobulked data across subtypes

```
srInt_agg <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/srInt_neurons_labeled_jung2023_filtered_cons_0.5
SD_0.2log2FCall_celltype_subset_agg.rds")

Idents(srInt_agg) <- "state"

pseudobulk_sq_state_neg_too <- RunPrestoAll(object = srInt_agg,
  test.use = "wilcox", return.thresh = 0.05, group.by = "state")

pseudobulk_sq_state_neg_too <- subset(pseudobulk_sq_state_neg_too,
  p_val_adj < 0.05)

saveRDS(pseudobulk_sq_state_neg_too, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/allbystate_resu
lts_list_negtoo_0.2log2FCall.rds")
```

Plot interesting findings

```
VlnPlot(srInt, "Upb1", group.by = "celltype", pt.size = 1, split.by = "state") +
  ggtitle("Upb1") + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 13),
  axis.title = element_text(size = 14))
```


Comments: Across the board, torpid neurons are enhancing expression of beta alanine synthase. Beta alanine is the excitatory ligand for 75% of NP nociceptors, which express Mrgprd. Are NP neurons getting additional excitation from an enhancement of beta alanine production? Another testable hypothesis.

End of RG 2023-2024 analysis.

Thanks for reading! Feel free to reach out with any questions, errors you found, or comments:
 rebecca.greenberg8@gmail.com

Acknowledgment: I owe a big thank you to Dr. Viktor Feketa for introducing me to bioinformatics, for his beautiful code examples, for his patience as he dealt with me, and, most importantly, for his unwavering commitment to truth.

Appendix

A. DoubletFinder continued

Explore the DoubletFinder output - how many doublets did we pick up here? Let's first add labels to metadata, and explore some doublet stats.

```

sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high.rds")
optimal.pk.list <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/optimal.pk.list.rds")
nExp_poi.adj.list <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/nExp_poi.adj.list.rds")

# Label doublet cells

for (i in names(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high)) {

  colname <- paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_", optimal.pk.list[[i]],
    "_", nExp_poi.adj.list[[i]])

  Doublet <- sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]]@meta.data[[colname]][which(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]]@m
eta.data[[colname]] ==
  "Doublet")]

  Singlet <- sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]]@meta.data[[colname]][which(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]]@m
eta.data[[colname]] ==
  "Singlet")]
}

# Show statistics!

counts_df <- data.frame(Seurat_Object = character(), Doublet_Count = numeric(),
  Singlet_Count = numeric(), Total_Count = numeric(), Percentage_Doublet = numeric(),
  stringsAsFactors = FALSE)

# Loop through each Seurat object in the list
for (i in names(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high)) {

  colname <- paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_", optimal.pk.list[[i]],
    "_", nExp_poi.adj.list[[i]])

  # Get indices of doublets and singlets
  doublet_indices <- which(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]]@meta.data[[colname]] ==
  "Doublet")
  singlet_indices <- which(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]]@meta.data[[colname]] ==
  "Singlet")

  # Calculate counts
  doublet_count <- length(doublet_indices)
  singlet_count <- length(singlet_indices)
  total_count <- doublet_count + singlet_count

  # Calculate percentage of doublets
  percentage_doublet <- doublet_count/total_count * 100

  # Store counts in the dataframe
  counts_df <- rbind(counts_df, data.frame(Seurat_Object = i,
    Doublet_Count = doublet_count, Singlet_Count = singlet_count,
    Total_Count = total_count, Percentage_Doublet = percentage_doublet))
}

# Print the dataframe
print(counts_df)

```

```

## Seurat_Object Doublet_Count Singlet_Count Total_Count Percentage_Doublet
## 1 tsqDRG1_F 5101 21135 26236 19.44275
## 2 tsqDRG2_M 5439 21890 27329 19.90194
## 3 tsqDRG3_F 6405 23243 29648 21.60348
## 4 asqDRG1_F 4903 21260 26163 18.74021
## 5 asqDRG2_F 2711 16807 19518 13.88974
## 6 asqDRG3_M 6585 23667 30252 21.76716
## 7 asqDRG4_F 8271 25477 33748 24.50812

```

What we are expecting: $0.008/1000 = ?/21135$, $?$ = around 17% for first sample. 27% for the last sample. Looks relatively good!

Extract your singlets, trash your doublets

To subset by singlets, let's create a new class to hold the high stringency DF...

```

# Create the final doublet classification field
for (i in names(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high)) {
  colname <- paste0("DF.classifications_0.25_", optimal.pk.list[[i]],
    "_", nExp.poi.adj.list[[i]])

  # Assign the classification field to the new class
  sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]][["doublet.class"]] <- sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]]@meta.data[,
    colname]
}

# Subset
sq_cluster_spd_qc_singlet <- list()

for (i in names(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high)) {
  sq_cluster_spd_qc_singlet[[i]] <- subset(sq_cluster_spd_qc_db_high[[i]],
    subset = doublet.class == "Singlet")
  print(sq_cluster_spd_qc_singlet[[i]])
}

```

```

## An object of class Seurat
## 38972 features across 21135 samples within 2 assays
## Active assay: SCT (18238 features, 3000 variable features)
## 3 layers present: counts, data, scale.data
## 1 other assay present: RNA
## 2 dimensional reductions calculated: pca, umap
## An object of class Seurat
## 38682 features across 21890 samples within 2 assays
## Active assay: SCT (17948 features, 3000 variable features)
## 3 layers present: counts, data, scale.data
## 1 other assay present: RNA
## 2 dimensional reductions calculated: pca, umap
## An object of class Seurat
## 38702 features across 23243 samples within 2 assays
## Active assay: SCT (17968 features, 3000 variable features)
## 3 layers present: counts, data, scale.data
## 1 other assay present: RNA
## 2 dimensional reductions calculated: pca, umap
## An object of class Seurat
## 38668 features across 21260 samples within 2 assays
## Active assay: SCT (17934 features, 3000 variable features)
## 3 layers present: counts, data, scale.data
## 1 other assay present: RNA
## 2 dimensional reductions calculated: pca, umap
## An object of class Seurat
## 37891 features across 16807 samples within 2 assays
## Active assay: SCT (17157 features, 3000 variable features)
## 3 layers present: counts, data, scale.data
## 1 other assay present: RNA
## 2 dimensional reductions calculated: pca, umap
## An object of class Seurat
## 38528 features across 23667 samples within 2 assays
## Active assay: SCT (17794 features, 3000 variable features)
## 3 layers present: counts, data, scale.data
## 1 other assay present: RNA
## 2 dimensional reductions calculated: pca, umap
## An object of class Seurat
## 38756 features across 25477 samples within 2 assays
## Active assay: SCT (18022 features, 3000 variable features)
## 3 layers present: counts, data, scale.data
## 1 other assay present: RNA
## 2 dimensional reductions calculated: pca, umap

```

```

# Double check you have the right amount of cells:

for (i in names(sq_cluster_spd_qc_singlet)) {

  print(ncol(sq_cluster_spd_qc_singlet[[i]]))
}

```

```
## [1] 21135
## [1] 21890
## [1] 23243
## [1] 21260
## [1] 16807
## [1] 23667
## [1] 25477
```

```
# Yes. you have single cells! Nice. Move on with rest of
# analysis!
```

```
saveRDS(sq_cluster_spd_qc_singlet, file = "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/sq_cluster_spd_qc_singlet.rds")
```

B. Let's output comprehensive excel sheets for genes of interest (pseudobulk DEG analyses)

What changes in torpor, by subtype? To make this even simpler, you can search for characters instead of genes.

```
results_list <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/insubtypebystate_results_list_negtoo_0.2log2F
Call.rds")

identities <- c("AB RA-LTMR Ntrk3", "Adelta-LTMR Ntrk2", "C-LTMR P2ry1",
               "Cold Trpm8", "NP1 Gfra1 Gfra2", "NP2 Gfra1", "NP3 Sst",
               "PEP1 Adcyap1", "PEP2 Fam19a1")

# Define the patterns for channel genes, marker lists, and
# mechano-related genes
channel_patterns <- c(".*cn.*", ".*Tmem.*", ".*Htr.*", ".*Asic.*",
                    ".*Gabra.*", ".*Gla.*", ".*Gria.*", ".*Grid.*", ".*Grik.*",
                    ".*Grin.*", ".*Itpr.*", ".*Chrn.*", ".*P2rx.*", ".*aqp.*",
                    ".*ano.*", ".*cftr.*", ".*Piezo.*", ".*orai.*", ".*opr.*",
                    ".*grm.*", ".*slc17a7.*", ".*slc17a6.*", ".*slc17a8.*", ".*slc32a1.*",
                    ".*slc1a.*", ".*slc6a.*", ".*drd.*", ".*adrb.*", ".*ucp.*",
                    ".*Gabbr.*", ".*slc12a.*", "Fam.*")
unwanted_patterns <- c(".*cnst.*", ".*cnot.*", ".*cnep.*", ".*ccn.*",
                    ".*pcnx.*", ".*cnt.*", ".*cnnm.*", ".*cnksr.*", ".*cnbd.*",
                    ".*tdrd.*")

# Combine patterns into single regular expressions
channel_pattern <- paste(channel_patterns, collapse = "|")
unwanted_pattern <- paste(unwanted_patterns, collapse = "|")

# Define marker lists

# Function to filter genes into upregulated and
# downregulated based on avg_log2FC
filter_genes <- function(results_df, order) {
  # Filter out unwanted genes based on unwanted patterns
  unwanted_genes <- grepl(unwanted_pattern, results_df$Genes,
                        ignore.case = TRUE)
  results_df <- results_df[!unwanted_genes, ]

  # Check if genes from marker lists are present
  genes_present <- grepl(channel_pattern, results_df$Genes,
                        ignore.case = TRUE) | results_df$Genes %in% c(markers_expand,
                        mechano_related, Trp_less)

  # Filter out unwanted genes
  results_df <- results_df[genes_present, ]

  # Separate into upregulated and downregulated genes
  upregulated_genes <- results_df[results_df$avg_log2FC > 0,
  ]
  downregulated_genes <- results_df[results_df$avg_log2FC <
  0, ]

  # Sort genes based on avg_log2FC
  if (order == "upregulated") {
    upregulated_genes <- upregulated_genes[order(upregulated_genes$avg_log2FC,
    decreasing = TRUE), ]
  }
}
```

```

} else {
  downregulated_genes <- downregulated_genes[order(downregulated_genes$avg_log2FC),
]
}

return(list(upregulated_genes = upregulated_genes, downregulated_genes = downregulated_genes))
}

# Create a new Excel workbook
wb <- createWorkbook()

# Iterate over each identity
for (identity in identities) {
  # Get the corresponding dataframe from results_list
  identity_df <- results_list[[identity]]

  # Filter genes into upregulated and downregulated
  filtered_genes_up <- filter_genes(identity_df, "upregulated")
  filtered_genes_down <- filter_genes(identity_df, "downregulated")

  upregulated_genes <- filtered_genes_up$upregulated_genes
  downregulated_genes <- filtered_genes_down$downregulated_genes

  # Add data to the Excel workbook
  addWorksheet(wb, paste0(identity, "_upregulated"))
  addWorksheet(wb, paste0(identity, "_downregulated"))
  writeData(wb, paste0(identity, "_upregulated"), upregulated_genes)
  writeData(wb, paste0(identity, "_downregulated"), downregulated_genes)
}

# Save the workbook
saveWorkbook(wb, "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/summary_torpid_within_neuronal_subtypes_0.
2log2FCall.xlsx",
  overwrite = TRUE)

```

What changes in torpor, across all subtypes?

```

results_list <- readRDS("~/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/allbystate_results_list_negtoo_0.2log2FCall.r
ds")

names(results_list)[names(results_list) == "cluster"] <- "state"

# Define the patterns for channel genes
channel_patterns <- c(".*cn.*", ".*Tmem.*", ".*Htr.*", ".*Asic.*",
  ".*Gabra.*", ".*Gla.*", ".*Gria.*", ".*Grid.*", ".*Grik.*",
  ".*Grin.*", ".*Itpr.*", ".*Chrn.*", ".*P2rx.*", ".*aqp.*",
  ".*ano.*", ".*cftr.*", ".*Piezo.*", ".*orai.*", ".*opr.*",
  ".*grm.*", ".*slc17a7.*", ".*slc17a6.*", ".*slc17a8.*", ".*slc32a1.*",
  ".*slc1a.*", ".*slc6a.*", ".*drd.*", ".*adrb.*", ".*Gabbr.*",
  ".*slc12a.*", "Fam.*")

# Combine patterns into a single regular expression
channel_pattern <- paste(channel_patterns, collapse = "|")

# Define the unwanted genes
unwanted_genes <- c("Cnot2", "Dcn", "Pcnx4", "Cnbd1", "Cnot8",
  "Ccnh", "Ccnk", "Ccnyl1", "Cntrl", "Anos1", "Ccndbp1", "Cneplr1",
  "Ccnl1", "Tdrd7")

# Check if genes from any of the marker lists or containing
# 'cn' are present
genes_present <- grepl(channel_pattern, results_list$gene, ignore.case = TRUE) |
  results_list$gene %in% c(mechano_related, markers_expand,
  Trp_less)

# Filter out unwanted genes from genes_present
genes_present <- genes_present & !results_list$gene %in% unwanted_genes

# Filter genes where state is 'torpid'
genes_present <- genes_present & results_list$state == "torpid"

# Filter upregulated and downregulated genes
upregulated_genes <- results_list[genes_present & results_list$avg_log2FC >
  0, ]
downregulated_genes <- results_list[genes_present & results_list$avg_log2FC <
  0, ]

# Sort genes in the upregulated tab by descending order of
# avg_log2FC
upregulated_genes <- upregulated_genes[order(upregulated_genes$avg_log2FC,
  decreasing = TRUE), ]

# Sort genes in the downregulated tab by ascending order of
# avg_log2FC
downregulated_genes <- downregulated_genes[order(downregulated_genes$avg_log2FC),
  ]

# Create a new Excel workbook
wb <- createWorkbook()

# Add data to the first tab (upregulated genes)
addWorksheet(wb, "upregulated")
writeData(wb, "upregulated", upregulated_genes)

# Add data to the second tab (downregulated genes)
addWorksheet(wb, "downregulated")
writeData(wb, "downregulated", downregulated_genes)

# Save the workbook
saveWorkbook(wb, "/home/rg828/ycga_work/snRNAseq_Analysis_2023/summary_torpid_across_neuronal_subtypes_0.
2log2FCall.xlsx",
  overwrite = TRUE)

```